

D6.6 - Fact Sheets for cluster projects and other core initiatives (Release 2)

Work Package	WP6 - Blue Cloud Roadmap, Exploitation & Sustainability Measures, and trans-European Liaisons
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Due Date	31.01.2023, M40
Submission Date	28.03.2023, M42
Version	1.0

Dissemination Level

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VERSIONING AND CONTRIBUTION HISTORY

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	13.12.2022	Sara Pittonet, Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Table of Content
0.2	19.01.2023	Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Inputs in Sections 2.1 and 2.2
0.5	20.02.2023	Sara Pittonet, Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT), Pasquale Pagano (CNR)	Additional inputs in Sections 1, 2 and 3
0.6	02.03.2023	Sara Pittonet, Rita Giuffrida (Trust-IT)	Executive summary and conclusions
0.7	23.03.2023	Dick Schaap (MARIS)	Review and edits
1.0	28.03.2023	Sara Pittonet (Trust-IT)	Final edits and upload

Executive summary

Since the start of the Blue-Cloud project in October 2019, Blue-Cloud has achieved significant results. Blue-Cloud Open Science platform introduced a “de facto” federation taking place at 3 levels: the data, the computing resources and the analytical services. For each of them Blue-Cloud orchestrated mechanisms that successfully established interoperability and resulted in a Data Discovery and Access Service, the Virtual Research Environment and five Virtual Laboratories. Blue-Cloud working environments are serving more than 1,300 users in total spread across 20 countries. 15 services released by Blue-Cloud are now available in the EOSC marketplace.

Creating the Blue-Cloud Open Science platform was a team-work activity. In the course of the project, Blue-Cloud established synergies in the Open Science, Blue Economy and Marine Research fields with E-infrastructures, Blue Data Infrastructures, and EU-funded projects as the project team believes that through collaboration and cooperation with initiatives operating in the same field, the value of Blue-Cloud services increases. The established synergies contributed to the design of the Blue-Cloud services, fostered the adoption of Blue-Cloud innovative open-science solutions and broadened the exploitation opportunities thus highlighting the need for long term sustainability.

The types of synergies established span from technical collaborations that exploit the potential offered by the Blue-Cloud infrastructure (Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services, of the Blue-Cloud demonstrators and VLabs, and of the Data Discovery and Access Services) to support of the development of the Blue-Cloud Roadmap to 2030, or to join communication and dissemination activities.

This deliverable summarises the main outcomes of the collaboration with projects and infrastructures in the form of fact sheets, which are also downloadable from the Blue-Cloud website.

The document is structured as follows:

- The first Chapter describes the methodology adopted to scout relevant synergies and get in contact with them. The section showcases also the types of synergies Blue-Cloud has established with research infrastructures and EU-funded initiatives. The Chapter is concluded by showing the most strategic synergies for which Blue-Cloud has signed a Memorandum of Understanding;
- The second Chapter presents the synergies established with research infrastructures and EU-funded projects in the form of fact sheets;
- The third Chapter introduces some of the synergies started in the course of Blue-Cloud that will be brought forward by the follow-up initiative Blue-Cloud 2026

This document is the second, and last, release of the *Blue-Cloud fact sheets for cluster projects and other core initiatives* and represents an update of the information collected and presented in its first version (D6.1).

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1. Overview of Blue-Cloud synergies in the Blue Economy and Open Science

Since the launch of Blue-Cloud, the project team has established relationships with key players in the blue economy and open science environments. The collaboration has been strengthened throughout the project's lifespan and helped Blue-Cloud receive higher visibility in the marine community. Furthermore, establishing synergies has supported Blue-Cloud in advancing with technical developments, all crucial elements to drive forward the project's exploitation and sustainability plan.

Providing practical frameworks to establish long-term collaborations with external partners has also proved to be a key element to amplify the effect of the Blue-Cloud's main achievements and engage with marine communities.

Following the work started in the first half of Blue-Cloud, the project team has continued to strengthen the cooperation with key actors in the marine ecosystem and open science fields, by focusing on opportunities that revolve around the Blue-Cloud main assets: the **Data Discovery and Access Service**, the **Cyber Infrastructure and Virtual Research Environment**, and the **Demonstrators**.

The synergies have also helped better define the **Blue-Cloud's 2030 strategic Roadmap** and reinforce technical developments of the **Blue-Cloud federated infrastructure**, crucial for the development of the initiative's exploitation plan.

The following sections present the work carried out by the Blue-Cloud team, in the second half of the project, to reinforce the collaboration with strategic synergies.

1.1. The approach

The approach adopted to identify and get in contact with the most relevant initiatives has been implemented since the launch of the Blue-Cloud project and presented in *D6.1 (Fact Sheets for cluster projects and other core initiatives (Release 1))*. As it proved to be successful, the team has continued to adopt the same way of working for the rest of the Blue-Cloud lifetime. The Blue-Cloud consortium has continuously updated the "inventory of initiatives" database, a collaborative document that now includes more than 100 contacts.

Organisation	Stakeholder category	Country	Mission	Main area	Demonstrator	URL	Contact Point name
AAnchor	Research & Acad	Portugal	The main ambition of AANCHOR is to	Climate Variability, Ocean Resources, marine	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://www.allatlanticocean.org/	Sofia Cordeiro
AtlantECO	EU-funded project	Italy	The ambition of AtlantECO is to	microbiomes, plastics, biogeochemistry, ecosystem service	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/view/101017422	SZN & Stephane PESANT
BeOpen	EU-funded project	Greece	BE OPEN aims to promote Open science & transport	Open science & transport	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://beopen-project.eu/	Afroditi Anagnostopolou
CoastObs	EU-funded project	Hungary	CoastObs is an EU H2020 funded project	EO-based products	All	https://coastobs.eu/	Annelies Hommersom
Cos4Cloud	Research & Acad	Spain	Cos4Cloud is addressing the	Citizen Science	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/	Jaume Piera
EMODNet	Infrastructure	Pan-European	Assembling marine data, products	Marine data & data products	Marine Environmental Indicators	http://www.emodnet.eu/	Jan Bart Calewaert
ENVRI-FAIR	Infrastructure	Germany	Make sure that all participating	Environmental science	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://envri.eu/home-envri-fair/	Dr. Andreas Petzold Zhiming Zhao
EOSC Enhance	Infrastructure	Greece	Enhancing the service provided	Enhancement of the EOSC Portal	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://www.eosc-portal.eu/en/	Carmela Asero
EOSC Pillar	EU-funded project	Italy		EOSC governance	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/	Fulvio Galeazzi
EOSCsecretariat.eu	EU-funded project	Belgium	EOSC Secretariat delivers 360	EOSC governance	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://www.eoscsecretariat.eu/	Andrea Grisilla, Technopolis Group
EUDAT	Infrastructure	Finland	Data is shared and preserved	heterogeneous research data management services and storage resources	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://www.eudat.eu/	Damien Lecarpentier
Euro-Argo	Infrastructure	Pan-European	Global array of more than 3500	Marine data & data products	Marine Environmental Indicators	https://www.euro-argo.eu/	Sylvie Pouliquen
EuroBioImaging	Blue Data Infrastructure	Pan-European	Access to biological and biomedical	biological and biomedical imaging data and instruments	Biodiversity	https://www.eurobioimaging.eu/	Frauke Leitner
EuroOBIS	Blue Data Infrastructure	The Netherlands	Online marine biogeographic	Biogeographic data	Biodiversity	http://www.eurobis.org/	Leen Vandepitte

Figure 1 Screenshot of some of the initiatives included in the inventory of initiatives

After identifying the most strategic collaborations, Trust-IT (WP6 task leader) organised a first introductory call with the WP2, WP3 teams and SeaScape Belgium (WP6 leader) to introduce Blue-Cloud and identify potential collaboration.

A summary overview of the outcomes of the calls were presented at the monthly Steering Board meetings to receive strategic guidance. Afterwards, further calls have been organised with representatives of Blue-Cloud WP2, WP3, and WP4 in case the projects expressed an interest towards the Blue-Cloud services; and WP5 members in case the cooperation was more oriented towards dissemination and communication activities. All the projects that expressed interest in contributing to the Blue-Cloud Roadmap, had follow-up calls with the WP6 team and were involved in the open consultations.

Moreover, starting from February 2021, at the end of each introductory call, the projects that expressed a strong interest in cooperating with Blue-Cloud were asked to compile a template to collect more detailed information about the synergy. The content gathered through these templates helped narrow the scope of collaboration and produce the factsheets presented in the following paragraphs.

Proposed Synergies Form

1. Project Information

Project Acronym and Title

URL:

Logo:

Project Coordinator:

Social Media channels:

Coordinator Country:

Project duration:

Funding Programme - Type of funding:

Consortium members:

Project mission

Suggested length: 200 words

Useful links

Please provide a link to any documents, videos or materials that you would like us to showcase on the Blue-Cloud website

2. Type of synergy

Your offer to Blue-Cloud

Please indicate which of the following Blue-Cloud service offerings your project could best contribute to [multiple choice allowed]:

- Data Access and Discovery Services
- Cyber Infrastructure and Virtual Research Environments
- Demonstrators

How you can benefit from Blue-Cloud

 Blue-Cloud has received funding from the European Union's Horizon programme call BG-07-2019-2020, topic (K) 2019 - Blue Cloud services, Grant Agreement No.851406

After discussion with the Blue-Cloud team, which one of the following activities would you like to implement? Please also comment on the selected activities and suggest some short/medium/long-term collaborative actions. [Suggested length: 300 words / type]

- Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services
- Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud
Please provide any additional information relevant to inject data into the BlueCloud demonstrators
- Demonstrators
Please indicate how you can benefit from the Blue-Cloud demonstrators:
 - Zoo and Phytoplankton EOY products
 - Plankton Genomics
 - Marine Environmental Indicators
 - Fish, a matter of scales
 - Aquaculture Monitor
- Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap
- Joint dissemination / communication activities

3. Other

Ongoing collaborations

Please indicate below if you are already collaborating with other projects or initiatives at national, European or international level and which could be of interest in the framework of the synergy with Blue-Cloud

Relevant upcoming activities

Please indicate below any upcoming activities that you'd like to share with the Blue-Cloud consortium

Anything else you'd like to add?

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Figure 2 Synergy template

Online pages have been created and published on the Blue-Cloud website based on the synergy templates and are available on a dedicated [synergy section](#) on the Blue-Cloud website.

The established cooperation are focused on 4 main areas:

- **Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services:** the established partnerships contributed to better connecting computing platforms and services on remote ones and better shape the VRE;
- **Data Discovery and Access Services:** the initiatives involved support the Blue-Cloud project in enabling users and machines to find and collect data from a broader array of marine data infrastructures. The cooperation with several EU projects and infrastructures contributed to improve the quality and offer of the service;
- **Contribution to the Blue-Cloud strategic Roadmap:** The projects involved in this type of collaboration contributed to shaping the Blue-Cloud roadmap by providing strategic guidelines and policy recommendations.
- **Communication and dissemination activities:** activities related to this type of synergy are associated with the organisation of webinars or physical workshops, writing of joint articles or newspieces, and support of promotional activities through social media channels

By March 2023 (M42), a total of 77 projects have been considered for cooperation with Blue-Cloud. The following paragraphs provide more details about the scope of each area of synergy. For 26 of these, 11 Data Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures and 15 EU-funded initiatives, collaboration

turned into effective actions, and individual factsheets were produced, collected in the sections below and available online in the main [Synergies area](#) of the Blue-Cloud website.

In order to strengthen the cooperation with some of the most strategic synergies, Blue-Cloud has signed 4 **Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs)** with the EU-funded projects AQUA-LIT, EuroSea, Jonas and JERICO, key initiatives in coastal monitoring, noise prevention, aquaculture and ocean forecasting systems. The MoU is an agreement with two or more parties that explains the terms and scope of the collaboration. While the MoU does not have legal validity, it states a strong willingness of the involved parties to cooperate together.

The list of the established synergies is summarised in the table below. Each of them is further detailed in the factsheets in the following chapters 2 and 3.

N	Project / Organisation	Synergy area	Stakeholder Category
1	D4SCIENCE Infrastructure	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
2	WekeO	Data Discovery and Access service Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
3	EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure	Data Discovery and Access service Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
4	EMODnet	Data Discovery and Access service Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
5	Socat	Data Discovery and Access service	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
6	Euro Argo	Data Discovery and Access service	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
7	SeaDataNet	Data Discovery and Access service Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
8	ENA	Data Discovery and Access service Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
9	ICOS	Data Discovery and Access service	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
10	Eurobis	Data Discovery and Access service	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
11	EcoTaxa	Data Discovery and Access service	Data Infrastructures & e-Infrastructures
12	AANChOR	Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
13	Aqua-Lit	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative

N	Project / Organisation	Synergy area	Stakeholder Category
14	AtlantECO	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
15	CoastObs	Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
16	Cos4Cloud	Data Discovery and Access service Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
17	DOORS	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Data Discovery and Access Service	EU-funded initiative
18	ENVI-Fair	Data Discovery and Access service Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
19	EOSC Future	Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
20	EuroSea	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
21	FNS-Cloud	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
22	FORCOAST	Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap	EU-funded initiative
23	ILIAD	Data Access and Discovery Service Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap ●Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
24	Jonas	Usage and exploitation of the Blue-Cloud VRE services Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
25	NEANIAS	Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative
26	ODYSSEA	Communication and Dissemination activities	EU-funded initiative

Table 1 Blue-Cloud synergies by M41

1.1.1. Collaborations that contribute to the implementation and evolution to Blue-Cloud Cyber Infrastructure and Virtual Research Environment

The Blue-Cloud [Virtual Research Environment \(VRE\)](#) provides computing platforms and analytical services to facilitate collaboration between researchers. It includes services that facilitate coordination between users and services supporting the execution of analytical tasks embedded in a distributed computing infrastructure. The VRE is based upon the existing D4Science e-infrastructure, which already hosts Virtual Labs and offers a variety of services, which can be adopted for Blue-Cloud.

The cooperation with synergies helped improve the implementation of the VRE and connect computing platforms across infrastructures, while respecting ownership, provenance and controlled access of data.

Some examples of synergies that integrate applications into the Blue-Cloud VREs include research infrastructures, like **WekEO**, **SeaDataNet**, **EMODnet**, **EurOBIS**, **EUDAT**, but also EU-funded initiatives, like **ENVRI-FAIR**, **JERICO**, **JONAS**, **DOORS** and **FNS-Cloud**.

In particular, **JERICO** or **JONAS** have brought to the development of new V Labs, respectively called **JERICO-CORE** and **JONAS**. JERICO-CORE is a multi-platform research infrastructure dedicated to a holistic appraisal of coastal marine system changes, and the JONAS V Lab addresses the issue of underwater noise in the Atlantic Seas. These two new Virtual Labs were developed respectively in November 2021 and August 2022 to support the Blue-Cloud community with cross-thematic services.

In order to encourage the creation of synergies in this area and given the high skill required to fully exploit the potential offered by the VRE platform, the **Blue-Cloud team has organised a training to present the VRE**. The online tutorial was organised on 7 October 2022 and led by Massimiliano Assante, IT Operations Manager at D4Science Infrastructure. The training was joined live by representatives of the projects JERICO, JONAS, EuroSea and DOORS, following their request of attending a live tutorial to better understand the VRE offer. The training was also recorded and uploaded on the [Blue-Cloud YouTube channel](#) and made available from the training area of the Blue-Cloud public website to let any interested researchers learn more about it at their pace and stimulate new cooperation opportunities.

1.1.2. Synergies to expand data availability via the Data Discovery and Access Service

The Blue Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service is one of the two main components of the Blue-Cloud technical framework (together with the VRE).

It facilitates discovery and retrieval of marine data sets and data products for external users. The Blue-Cloud data sets are managed in Blue Data Infrastructures (BDIs) that are connected to the Blue-Cloud service to serve federated discovery and access. So far the following Blue Data Infrastructures have been federated: SeaDataNet, EMODnet Bathymetry, EMODnet Chemistry, EurOBIS – EMODnet Biology, Euro-Argo and Argo GDAC, ELIXIR-ENA, EcoTaxa, ICOS-Marine, and ICOS-SOCAT.

These BDIs are mostly complementary to each other, dealing with other data originators and/or different stages in the processing chains from data acquisition to data products to knowledge.

The Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service benefits both users and BDIs:

- Users:
 - Federated search for discovering interesting data sets (currently more than 10 million) in a common way
 - Federated retrieval of identified data sets using a shopping basket mechanism
 - Download of data sets or push to Blue-Cloud VRE
- Managers of BDIs:
 - Wider outreach to potential users
 - Stay informed about data requests and users for their repository
 - Periodic reporting of downloads from their repository

Blue-Cloud is a front runner of Data federation in EOSC, given its success in bringing together 9 data providers covering more than 10M datasets from the marine domain and making them available via the Data Discovery and Access Service (DD&AS) and the VRE to users, allowing interactions between disciplines, thus demonstrating the value of bringing together a variety of providers and users within EOSC.

Blue-Cloud engaged with other marine RIs, that are collecting and managing marine and ocean data, such as **JERICO-RI** (coastal observations) , **DOORS**, and **BRIDGES** (both aimed at the Black Sea region), promoting awareness about Blue-Cloud approach and services, and establishing more interaction and feedback on performance and relevance of Blue-Cloud services.. With respect to the Blue-Cloud DD&AS, all three projects were advised and encouraged to make their new to be acquired data sets part of the leading European marine data management infrastructures such as SeaDataNet and EuroBIS, by which their data sets would also become included in the Blue-Cloud DD&AS through the federation.

1.1.3. Synergies supporting the Blue-Cloud strategic Roadmap

One of the main outputs of the Blue-Cloud project is its **strategic Roadmap to 2030**. The Roadmap is a policy document providing the basis for the future strategic development of the Blue-Cloud system in the wider marine community and as a component of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). As a matter of fact, the Blue-Cloud Roadmap investigates how Blue-Cloud can effectively and efficiently contribute to address the above goals. It considers technical developments, user demand and needs, market analysis and opportunities for exploitation of Blue-Cloud resources, while providing options that ensure sustainability of Blue-Cloud services and interoperability with the EOSC ecosystem.

Project synergies have contributed to shaping the Blue-Cloud roadmap by providing strategic guidelines and policy recommendations. Examples are coming from representatives of EU-funded initiatives, such as **EuroSea**, **FNS-Cloud**, **ENVRI-FAIR**, or **Cos4Cloud**.

1.1.4. Synergies on Communication and dissemination activities

Cooperating through communication and dissemination activities help projects amplify the effects of their outcomes by reaching a broader community. Activities related to this type of synergy are associated with the organisation of webinars or physical workshops, writing of joint articles or newspieces, and support of promotional activities through social media channels. Blue-Cloud has established this type of synergy with almost all the engaged initiatives.

1.1.5. Further exploitation of Blue-Cloud Demonstrators and V Labs

Blue-Cloud developed [5 real-life demonstrators](#) covering topics related to Biodiversity, Genomics, Marine Environmental Indicators, Fisheries and Aquaculture. Each demonstrator offers services which are accessible through virtual laboratories (or V Labs) reachable through the VRE. Initiatives interested in cooperating in this area, help increase the quantity and quality of data to better shape, in this way, analysis¹.

In addition to this, the **Blue-Cloud Hackathon**, which was held in February 2022, stimulated the creation of **Pilots** to explore and test Blue-Cloud. More than 150 passionate ocean researchers were challenged to develop applications that contribute to improving **knowledge of marine ecosystems**, support the transition to a **greener blue economy** and advance Ocean literacy. Details about how the Hackathon pilots exploited the resources and datasets produced by the Virtual Labs are provided in D5.3 Blue-Cloud Services Uptake Report

1.1.6. Memorandum of Understanding (MoU)

In order to strengthen the cooperation with some of the most strategic synergies, Blue-Cloud has signed 4 **Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs)** throughout its lifetime. The MoU is an agreement with two or more parties that explains the terms and scope of the collaboration. While the MoU does not have legal validity, it states a strong willingness of the involved parties to cooperate together.

Thanks to the signature of these documents, Blue-Cloud has established durable cooperation with the EU-funded projects AQUA-LIT, EuroSea, JONAS and JERICO, key initiatives in coastal monitoring, noise prevention, aquaculture and ocean forecasting systems.

The MoUs were signed between October 2021 and April 2022, as shown in the table below:

¹ See Blue-Cloud D3.5. Pilot Demonstrators Principal Results, Achievements & Actionable Items for the Future Report

Project name	Date of MoU signature
AQUA-LIT	25/01/2022
EuroSea	17/02/2022
JONAS	29/10/2021
JERICO	28/04/2022

Table 2 Dates of MoU signature

The information stated in the signed MoUs are the following:

- Legal information of the entities involved in the signature of the MoU;
- Description of the projects' objectives;
- Scope of the collaboration;
- Copyright and use of the parties documents;
- Duration and termination;
- Terms.

These joint efforts are strategic to help Blue-Cloud increase and improve its service offer, and support the development of a long-term sustainable action plan in the aquaculture, ocean noise monitoring, marine coastal science and ocean observing and forecasting systems fields.

2. Factsheets for cluster projects and other initiatives

The following sections present an update of the collaboration activities between Blue-Cloud and research infrastructures, data infrastructures and EU-funded projects, already presented in D6.1 and aligned with the categorisation introduced above.

2.1. E-Infrastructures

Blue-Cloud provides a cloud-based, analytical and publishing framework as a federation of computing platforms and analytical services, hosted at leading e-infrastructures, offered through an easy-to-use orchestration system to access cloud computing resources distributed at different cloud providers sites. The e-infrastructures federated to Blue-Cloud and their direct contribution to the project are listed below.

2.1.1. D4Science

About

The D4Science e-infrastructure is at the core of the Blue-Cloud VRE's. D4Science core services are used for building and running Virtual Labs, which are VRE's that are dedicated to specific research objectives. The

D4SCIENCE

D4Science e-infrastructure implements proven solutions for connecting to external services and orchestrates distributed services, which will be instrumental for smart connections to other e-infrastructures in Blue-Cloud, including EUDAT and DIAS (WekEO). Each VLab enables services and data exploitation to its authorized users.

Coverage

D4Science serves different domains in 50+ countries worldwide. D4Science hosts more than 165 Virtual Research Environments (VREs) to serve the biological, ecological, environmental, social mining, culture heritage, and statistical communities world-wide.

Core Services

D4Science Security: D4Science provides access to a set of services hosted by different organisations in the EU. The connection between the sites is secured through Transport Level Security (TLS), which provides communication security over the computer network.

D4Science ensures privacy and data integrity between two communicating computer applications. In particular, any connection between a client (e.g., a web browser) and a D4Science server has the following properties:

- Private (or secure) connection through the adoption of symmetric cryptography, which encrypts the data transmitted. The keys for this symmetric encryption are uniquely generated for each connection and are based on a shared secret (negotiated at the start of the session). The server and client negotiate the details about which encryption algorithm and cryptographic keys shall be used before data are transmitted. The negotiation of a shared secret is both secure, as it is unavailable to eavesdroppers (and even not to attackers who place themselves in the middle of the connection). For this reason, D4Science is

reliable, as no attacker can modify the communications during the negotiation without being detected.

- Authentication of communicating parties happens by using public-key cryptography. This authentication can be made optional on the client's side; however, it is ensured on the server's side.
- Integrity of the connection is ensured as each information transmitted is linked to a message authentication code to prevent undetected loss or alteration of the data during the transmission.
- Forward secrecy ensures that a future disclosure of encryption keys cannot be applied to decrypt any TLS communications recorded in the past.

Function in Blue-Cloud

VRE Management	Service to enable authorized users (i.e. VRE Managers) to dynamically create VLabs and manage their users. VRE Managers can (i) authorize users to access VLabs, (ii) assign or withdraw roles to users, (iii) remove users, and (iv) send communications to the current users.
Collaboration Framework	Set of social tools to share data, updates and messages with others and to keep abreast of new data, prospects, services, users.
Workspace	Service to enable every user to store and organise the information objects he/she is interested in working with. In addition to that, the user is allowed to collaborate with other users by sharing objects and messages. 100 GB storage volume is guaranteed to every user.
Secure File Sharing and Storage	Service to enable secure and controlled file sharing.
Accounting Framework	Service enabling accounting resource usage and usage control via quota mechanisms.
Data Analytics Framework	A set of data analytics services including: (i) the DataMiner engine (a rich array of ready to use analytical methods ranging from data clustering methods to geospatial data analytics, occurrence data management, and species distribution maps generation); (ii) the Software and Algorithms Importer (SAI) (an interface allowing any user to easily and quickly import scripts into DataMiner); (iii) the RStudio suite allowing its users to perform online statistical analyses with R; (iv) the JupyterHub, a web-based interactive development environment for Jupyter notebooks, code, and data. It allows users to configure and arrange the user interface to support a wide range of workflows in data science, scientific computing, and machine learning.
SDI	The SDI (Spatial Data Infrastructure) provides users with the capability to store, discover, access, and manage vectoral and raster georeferenced datasets. The SDI exploits the following technologies: GeoServer equipped with PostgreSQL and PostGIS, GeoNetwork, Thredds. All the exploited technologies are fully integrated and deployed to ensure fault-tolerance, load-balancing, controlled and secure access, monitoring and accounting.

Publishing Framework	The Publishing Framework includes a set of services and components enabling their users to document and make “public” (made available online) any generated product. Its primary component is the VRE Data Catalogue. The VRE Data Catalogue service is a catalogue service built on open-source technology for data catalogues (CKAN ckan.org), but extended to (a) be integrated with D4Science services, (b) support a rich, community-defined, and extensible set of catalogue item typologies, and (c) manage publications for each VLab and automatic integration at Blue-Cloud VRE.
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Table 2 – D4Science role in Blue-Cloud

URL: D4Science.org

Partners involved: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)

Factsheet available at <https://www.blue-cloud.org/e-infrastructures/d4science>

2.1.2. WEKEO - DIAS

About

WEKEO is one of the 5 Copernicus DIAS (Data and Information Access Services). The overarching objective of DIAS is to enhance access to Copernicus data and information for further use in an efficient computing environment implementing the paradigm of “bringing the user to the data”, as one condition for unlocking the potential value of Copernicus for innovation, science, new business, implementation of public policies and economic growth.

Considering the well-structured user communities and the strong relationship existing between EUMETSAT, Mercator-Océan and ECMWF, Copernicus ClimateChange Service, the organisations have joined their efforts to implement one instance of DIAS in partnership, namely WEKEO. WEKEO is the service for marine environmental data, virtual environments for data processing, and skilled user support. WEKEO has a public and free part for discovery and access to data and data products, while it also has a commercial part with various analysis applications and cloud space.

Coverage

The Harmonized Data Access (HAD) provides a single access protocol (REST API) whereby scaling and evolution of codes are made easy. This way, it provides easy & fast access to subsetting attributes in hundreds of datasets from different Copernicus sources and allows uniform access to the whole WEKEO catalogue, including subsetting and downloading functionalities. The HAD provides discovery and access to:

- All the Sentinel satellite data sets: S1, S2, S3 Marine, S3 Land, S5P
- Main Copernicus Service Data products from:
 - Copernicus Marine Service:
 - CMEMS Copernicus Atmospheric Service: CAMS
 - Copernicus Climate Service: C3S
 - Copernicus Land Service: CLMS

Figure 3 Example of data aggregation from WEkEO

Function in Blue-Cloud:

- Multi-Source viewer (free access): Viewer able to present Satellite Imagery, in-situ data, and model-based data. Capability to handle information from different height and depth layers, and information in changing in time (past-present-future), from model. Data discovery is enabled by the connection of the viewer to WEkEO Catalogue, enabling browsing and selection of datasets and their associated metadata.
- Access to information pages (free access): Tutorials, wiki, forums.
- Access to the WEkEO helpdesk (free access).
- Access to Jupyter Notebooks (free access): provide computing resources and a virtual environment for launching processing on data.
- Build and deploy your own front office and hosted processing (with subscription).
- Access to VM catalogue with preinstalled applications and optimized networking to the data storage layer (with subscription).
- Access to additional storage and cloud services for hosting your data and making it available to your tenants or to a wider audience through tailored means (with subscription).
- Access to Morpheus cloud management interfaces and manage all your tenants (with subscription).

URL: <https://www.wekeo.eu/>

Partners involved: Mercator Ocean

Factsheet available at <https://www.blue-cloud.org/e-infrastructures/wekeo-dias>

2.1.3. EUDAT

About

EUDAT offers heterogeneous research data management services and storage resources, supporting multiple research communities, through its network of academic computing and data centres across 15 European nations, whereby data is stored alongside some of Europe's most powerful supercomputers. European researchers can preserve, find, access, and process data in a trusted environment, as part of the EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure. One of EUDAT's main ambitions is to bridge the gap between research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures through an active engagement strategy. It is supported by EU DG RTD and EU DG CONNECT.

EUDAT is one of the horizontal e-infrastructures (EUDAT, DIAS, D4Science) that are aimed to capitalise on what already exists and to develop and deploy the Blue Cloud framework.

Core Services

EUDAT has developed a service stack that forms the Collaborative Data Infrastructure (CDI). The services are as follows:

- B2SAFE, Replicate Research Data Safely.
- B2STAGE, Get Data to Computation.
- B2FIND, Find Research Data.
- B2SHARE, Store, Share and Publish Research Data.
- B2DROP, Sync and Exchange Research Data.

In addition, a set of EUDAT core operational services, essential for the management of the CDI have been defined as follows:

- B2ACCESS (identity and authorisation), easy-to-use and secure Authentication and Authorisation platform.
- B2HANDLE (Persistent IDentification (PID) management), a service to register persistent identifiers called Handles to data objects and retrieve data objects via these identifiers, serving a purpose similar to DOIs for papers.
- B2HOST, a Service Hosting Framework that allows communities to deploy and operate their own applications and data-oriented services on machines next to the data storage.

Function in Blue-Cloud:

The horizontal e-infrastructure EUDAT is a component in the "Blue Cloud" e-infrastructures framework.

EUDAT has leveraged its suite of B2SERVICES (B2ACCESS, B2SAFE, B2STAGE, B2HOST, and B2DROP) and expertise to contribute to the following Blue-Cloud achievements:

- To be part of the data broker that facilitates the Data Discovery & Access Service to retrieve selected data sets from the federated Blue-Cloud data infrastructures and to store these in a temporary data cache, together with associated metadata; .
- To deliver the selected and retrieved data sets to users or to push these into the VRE for use in V Labs for computing, analytical and visualization services.
- Making the Blue-Cloud DD&AS and the VRE Products catalogues interoperable and accessible via the EOSC portal, using OAI-PMH protocols.

URL: <https://eudat.eu/>

Partners involved: Trust-IT, CSC, CINECA, DKRZ

Factsheet available at: <https://www.blue-cloud.org/e-infrastructures/eudat>

2.2. Blue Data Infrastructures

The 9 Data infrastructures federated into the Blue-Cloud pilot platform are listed below.

2.2.1. EcoTaxa

About

EcoTaxa is a web application dedicated to the visual exploration and the taxonomic identification of images of plankton. EcoTaxa was born from the experience developed at Laboratoire d'Océanographie de Villefranche (LOV) regarding the quantitative, high-throughput imaging of plankton and of the Oceanomics project which exploited the data collected during the Tara Oceans cruise, including quantitative imaging. It is now developed mainly through the WWWPIC project funded by the Belmont Forum and as part of the Blue-Cloud project.

The aim of EcoTaxa is to centralise images of plankton, to allow their collaborative classification along a universal taxonomy and to accelerate this process through machine learning. It produces ecological data in the form of concentration and biovolume of organisms in a given taxon, at a given point in latitude, longitude, depth and time. Visitors have free access to the specimens that have been already identified by taxonomist experts. They can explore the database by navigating along a taxonomic tree. Then images can be filtered according to several sampling criteria (location, time, etc.). For operators, easy-to-use tools are provided to suggest a classification for each image over large datasets, through supervised machine learning.

Type & number of data sets

Currently, EcoTaxa contains circa 150 million images of which circa 63 million have been annotated in over 2000 datasets. Of these, circa 30 million images concern living organisms. The growth rate is circa 4 million new images per month. Not all of these datasets will be accessible for Blue-Cloud, because this depends on the data policy of data providers, who come from circa 350 organisations worldwide. Some of those datasets (in particular the Tara Oceans ones, needed by the demonstrators) will be sent from EcoTaxa to EMODnet Biology and be harvested by the Blue-Cloud data discovery service from there. Then, Blue Cloud users will be able to browse them in finer details through the EcoTaxa API.

Figure 4 EcoTaxa dashboard for annotation

Core Services

The core of EcoTaxa is the rapid identification of large numbers of images by a combination of machine learning and human validation. The resulting data can be browsed and downloaded once access to the dataset is granted by the dataset owner.

Data discovery used to be manual. Validated data from all public datasets can be browsed at <https://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/explore/>. As part of the WWVPIC and Blue-Cloud projects an Application Programming Interface was built to allow programmatic browsing of public datasets that were uploaded to EMODnet Biology.

Figure 5 EcoTaxa interface for exploring images

Function in Blue-Cloud. Thanks to the collaboration within Blue-Cloud, EcoTaxa can accelerate data processing and sharing for the “Zoo & Phytoplankton EOVS Products” and “Plankton Genomics” Demonstrators. Within the goal of Blue-Cloud to federate information from different databases at EU level, EcoTaxa contributes data to EMODnet Biology, which is then aggregated in Blue-Cloud’s data discovery service, and also provides finer scale data as a second level of query.

URL: <http://ecotaxa.obs-vlfr.fr/>

Partners involved: Sorbonne University

Factsheet available at <https://www.blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/ecotaxa>

2.2.2. EMODnet

About

The European Marine Observation and Data network (EMODnet) was initiated in 2008 and it is a long-term marine data initiative funded by the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (managed by EU DG MARE).

EMODnet, together with the Copernicus Earth Observation programme and the Data Collection Framework for fisheries, implements the EU’s Marine Knowledge 2020 strategy. The EMODnet network connects to over 150 organisations supported by the EU’s Integrated Maritime Policy who work together to observe the sea, process the data according to international standards, and make that information freely available as interoperable data layers and data products. For this purpose, EMODnet works closely together with other existing infrastructures, such as the EuroGOOS ROOS’s for operational oceanography data exchange, the ICES international data centre, and European

research infrastructures, such as SeaDataNet, EurOBIS, EGDI, and others to bring together data sets from hundreds in-situ data collectors from science, government, and industry. A major added value of EMODnet is the generation and free publishing of a range of European wide derived data products that serve many user communities. Moreover, the EMODnet initiative has and is mobilising many data collectors to get connected to the data exchange infrastructures for sharing their data with EMODnet, contributing to better data products. To that end, EMODnet also operates EMODnet Ingestion as a service and network of experienced data centres to identify, convince, and provide support to data collectors to join the European marine data exchange, both for Near Real-Time and delayed mode data types. It has been estimated that this kind of integrated marine data policy will save off-shore operators at least one billion Euro per year, as well as opening up new opportunities for innovation and growth. EMODnet provides easy and free access to marine data, metadata and data products and services spanning seven broad disciplinary themes: bathymetry, geology, physics, chemistry, biology, seabed habitats and human activities. The aim of EMODnet is to increase productivity in all tasks involving marine data, to promote innovation and to reduce uncertainty about the behaviour of the sea. This will lessen the risks associated with private and public investments in the blue economy, and facilitate more effective protection of the marine environment.

Type and number of data sets

EMODnet develops interoperable services that simplify the interaction between different machines and promote the exchange of European seas and ocean data and metadata. EMODnet offers more than 800.000 datasets and registered more than 140.000 manual data download requests and more than 1.300.000 web services transactions in the last 2 years.

The EMODnet offerings

EMODnet develops interoperable services that simplify the interaction between different machines and promote the exchange of European seas and ocean data and metadata. Both data and data products are available. The data products are free to download and are published under Open Data licences. These data products are derived from the data that is also available through EMODnet. Much of this data is also freely available. However, in some situations, restrictions to access and use may apply. EMODnet makes data and data products available via web services, which enable machine to machine communication. In general, the web services conform to two architectural approaches:

- Geospatial web services that conform to Open Geospatial Standards (OGC):
 - Web mapping services (WMS), widespread usage in EMODnet
 - Web feature services (WFS), limited usage in EMODnet
 - Web catalogue service (CSW), limited usage in EMODnet
- Restful web services for subsetting and downloading data. These Restful web services conform to the OpenDAP standard. They are mainly used with gridded data (NetCDF files) and data from sensors. These web services also offer data conversion via web processing services.

Core Services

EMODnet offers the following data and products via web services:

- Temperature and Salinity in the water column
- Sea Surface Currents
- River Runoff Data
- Total Suspended Matter
- Impulsive Noise Event Registry
- Sound Maps
- Ice Extent and Ice-type
- Wave and winds – Sea State
- Water quality data collections and derived maps
- Marine Litter data collections and derived maps
- Bathymetry by means of a Digital Terrain Model of the European seas
- Geology by means of a series of geological maps
- Human activities with topical maps
- Seabed habitat maps
- and many more

Recently, all thematic portals have been migrated and become part of one central EMODnet portal, where all products and services can be found by users. While, the thematic groups continue to be responsible for the product developments and running the web services which are underpinning the user interface services in the central EMODnet portal.

Function in Blue-Cloud

Some EMODnet portals are already exploring the use of Virtual Research Environments for speeding up product generation chains, for validating and harmonising the processing of large collections of data sets and for generating derived data products. Therefore, EMODnet has an interest in the VRE activities of the Blue-Cloud, next to providing access to its harmonised data collections through the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service and for use in the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and its Virtual Labs.

In particular, Blue-Cloud Virtual Labs are integrating diverse data from EMODnet. For example, biodiversity and environmental data (relevant for Plankton Genomics), physics, biology, chemistry data (relevant for Marine Environmental Indicators), biology and coastlines data (relevant for Fish, a matter of scales), and in-situ environmental data for ground-truthing and European marine topography (relevant for Aquaculture Monitor).

Moreover, the EMODnet potential is exploited to create a bridge between Blue-Cloud and the other EU-funded projects the consortium has established synergies with (e.g. AQUA-LIT, ENVRI-FAIR).

Partners involved: MARIS, IFREMER, SSBE, VLIZ

URL: <http://www.emodnet.eu/>

Factsheet available at <https://www.blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/emodnet-central-portal>

2.2.3. ENA

About

The European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) provides a comprehensive open record of the world's nucleotide sequencing information and a platform for the management and analysis of sequence and related data for a wide range of applications in ocean science. Elixir is the coordinating research infrastructure for life science data in Europe.

The ENA system contains many data types/classes and a huge volume of data, which are only partly marine-related. Blue-Cloud focuses on data and information relevant for the marine domain and on data types such as samples and their analyses. Moreover, the ENA system offers several algorithms/pipelines for processing data, which might be used in a 'smart' way for the Blue-Cloud.

Type & number of data sets

ENA covers many data types in a number of interlinked database tables. A list can be found at <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/results?dataPortal=ena>

Data can be retrieved in different formats and with easy file download options through RESTful services: EMBL Flatfile format, FASTA format for sequences and XML Format. Details about formats: <https://ena-browser-docs.readthedocs.io/en/latest/browser/search/advanced.html#downloadena-records>

Figure 6 Illustration of growth of selected data types since March 2016

Core Services

The [ENA browser](#) brings together a set of services via web interfaces, build upon underlying APIs. Of relevance for Blue-Cloud are two services:

- ENA Data Discovery (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/advanced-search>)
- ENA Data Retrieval (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>)

How to use the API's and build machine-to-machine services can be found in the documentation of the ENA Portal API: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/portal/api/doc>

Function in Blue-Cloud

EMBL-EBI operates APIs for ENA discovery and ENA data retrieval, which are suitable endpoints for connecting to the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access service. The ENA system contains many data types / classes and a huge volume of data, which are only partly marine-related. ENA stands to benefit from the Blue-Cloud project because the project allows it to connect to all these different data types and allows scientists to access in an interdisciplinary way all these data.

Particularly contributing to the development of the Plankton Genomics demonstrator, the data provided by ENA allow the demonstrator team to pull out individual organisms and signatures of organisms in the sequence from different environments, and then to correlate them with the environmental factors that come with these data sources.

Partners involved: EMBL

URL: <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/about>

Factsheet available at <https://www.blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/ena>

2.2.4. Euro-Argo ERIC

About

The Euro-Argo ERIC allows active coordination and strengthening of the European contribution to the international Argo program. Its main objectives are to provide, deploy and operate the European contribution to the global array of Argo floats (currently around 800 floats, ¼ of the global array) and an enhanced coverage of European seas, to expand towards biogeochemistry, greater depths and high latitudes and to provide access to quality-controlled data and derived products.

The Euro-Argo ERIC also provides access to quality-controlled data and derived products: Core-Argo array and BGC-Argo array.

Core-Argo array. The broad-scale global array of temperature/salinity profiling floats, known as Argo, has already grown to be a major component of the ocean observing system. Argo is a standard, which is an example for other developing ocean observing systems. Argo provides good examples on various topics such as how to collaborate internationally, how to develop a data management system, and how to change the way scientists think about collecting data. Argo float deployments began in 2000 and currently there are circa 4000 Argo floats active.

BGC-Argo array. Biogeochemical-Argo aims at developing a global network of biogeochemical sensors on Argo profiling floats. The concept of global robotic biogeochemical measurements was articulated in a Community White Paper (Gruber et al., 2007) that was supported by the International Ocean Carbon Coordinating Project (IOCCP) and the US Ocean Carbon and Biogeochemistry Program (US-OCB).

Target for the global array is to have 1000 fully equipped BGC-Argo active floats with a uniform spatial distribution. Euro-Argo aims at contributing to ¼ of the global effort, which represents 250 active BGC floats. These will collect next to the regular Temperature, Salinity and Depth the following BGC parameters: Oxygen concentration; Nitrate concentration; pH; Chlorophyll a concentration; Suspended particles; and Downwelling irradiance.

The EuroArgo portal features a dashboard which provides a facet search including dynamic map for discovery of Argo floats and open access to its data sets. Also, it is possible to retrieve the whole Argo data collection by a DOI and associated landing page with descriptive metadata about the collection. Note: In the framework of ENVRI-FAIR and EOSC-hub, a development is underway for an additional data discovery and access service.

Figure 7 Overview of Argo organisation

Type & number of data sets

Argo collects salinity/temperature and biogeochemical profiles from an array of robotic floats that populate the ice-free oceans that are deeper than about 2000m. They also give information on the surface and subsurface currents. Most profiles are made up of about 200 (Argos) to 1000 (Iridium) data points (vertical resolution). In total, there are currently 16.000 Argo floats which generated more than 2 million files. Metadata and data for profiles and trajectories, including technical information are made available as NetCDF (CF) files.

In addition, Argo products are generated and made available as gridded fields.

Figure 8 Overview map of EuroArgo floats – January 2020

Core Services

The following web services are provided:

- GDAC synchronization service (rsync) - <http://www.argodatamgt.org/Access-to-data/Argo-GDAC-synchronization-service>
- GDAC Thredds server API - <http://tds0.ifremer.fr/thredds/catalog/CORIOLIS-ARGO-GDAC-OBS/catalog.html>
- GDAC ERDDAP data server API - <https://erddap.ifremer.fr/erddap/tabledap/ArgoFloats.graph>

Moreover, it is possible to visualise the Euro-Argo's main services through a dashboard, as shown in the figure below.

Figure 9 Facet search of Argo floats via dashboard Function in Blue-Cloud

Euro-Argo explores machine learning for data quality assessment to capitalise on what already exists and to develop and deploy the Blue-Cloud as a platform bringing together and providing access to:

- multidisciplinary data from observations and models,
- analytical tools,
- computing facilities that are essential for key blue science use cases.

Euro-Argo contributes to the development of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access service as one of the blue data infrastructures giving access to the Argo data sets. Moreover, Euro-Argo implements a workflow to apply big data analysis and machine learning (e.g. neural networks) methods on the multi-source data sets, which is an interesting input for the Virtual Labs.

Moreover, Euro-Argo is involved in exploiting the Blue-Cloud demonstrators providing access to salinity, oxygen, chlorophyll data (relevant for Zoo and Phytoplankton EOVI products), environmental data (relevant for Plankton Genomics) and salinity, oxygen, chlorophyll data (relevant for Marine Environmental Indicators).

Partners involved: Ifremer

URL: <https://fleetmonitoring.euro-argo.eu/dashboard>

Factsheet available at <https://www.blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/euroargo-argo>

2.2.5. Eurobis

About

EMODnet biology is a thematic group of EMODnet providing free access to data on temporal and spatial distribution of marine species and species traits from all European regional seas. It is built upon the World Register of Marine Species and the European Ocean Biogeographic Information System. EMODnet Biology aims to provide a single access point to European marine biodiversity data and products by assembling individual datasets from various sources and processing them into interoperable data products for assessing the environmental state of ecosystems and sea basins.

Type & number of data sets

EurOBIS was developed by the Flanders Marine Institute in 2004, within the framework of the MarBEF project (MARine Biodiversity and Ecosystem Functioning). It brings together biogeographic data collected within European marine waters, or by European researchers and institutes outside Europe. It focuses on taxonomy and distribution records in space and time and offers a number of online tools to easily query and visualise the data. Currently, EurOBIS holds **956 datasets, representing 62.299 species and 24 million distribution records**. With more than 6 million distribution records, fish are the most common in the database, followed by (sea) birds and marine mammals.

Over the years, the EurOBIS database structure has evolved, making it possible to not only capture presence or abundance of species, but also e.g. biomass data and length measurements in a standardised and structured way. Remarkably, even ‘blubber thickness in marine mammals’ is part of the EurOBIS information system, with 247 measurements made on the beach, in species such as harbour porpoise, grey seal, harbour seal, white-beaked dolphin or bottlenose dolphin.

Core Services

The data can be discovered and accessed by means of the Data Catalog or the Data Download Toolbox. The data discovery and access services are available from the EMODnet Biology website.

- [Data Catalog](#)
- [Data Download Toolbox](#)

The architecture of the EurOBIS – EMODnet Biology system is illustrated below:

Figure 10 EurOBIS – EMODnet Biology system architecture and metadata – data flow

The IPT stands for service [Integrated Publishing Toolkit \(IPT\)](#). This could be very suitable as catalogue / discovery service endpoint for the Blue-Cloud data discovery and access.

INTEGRATED PUBLISHING TOOLKIT (IPT)
 free and open access to biodiversity data

ENGLISH

[Home](#) [About](#)

Hosted resources available through this IPT

Filter:

Logo	Name	Organisation	Type	Subtype	Records	Last modified	Last publication	Next publication
--	1507-1997 Paul F. Clark North East Atlantic Crab Atlas	Not registered	Sampling event	--	10,989	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--
--	1778-1998 Ivor Rees North Wales Marine Fauna Ad-hoc sightings shore and ship-based surveys	Not registered	Sampling event	--	6,566	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--
--	1915-2016 Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) Collation of invasive non-indigenous species data UK	Not registered	Sampling event	--	9,147	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--
--	2005-Ongoing UK MarLIN Shore Thing timed search results	Not registered	Occurrence	Observation	10,404	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--
--	2012-ongoing UK Offshore Marine Conservation Zone (MCZ) Survey Data	Not registered	Sampling event	--	6,030	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--
--	70 samples data of Kiel Bay	Flanders Marine Institute (VLIZ)	Occurrence	Observation	1,144	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--
--	A comparison of benthic biodiversity in the North Sea	Not registered	Occurrence	Observation	2,589	2019-12-23	2019-12-23	--

Figure 11 EurOBIS – EMODnet Biology IPT service

Figure 12 EMODnet Biology website

Function in Blue-Cloud

The EurOBIS data, in particular the Continuous Plankton Recorder dataset from the UK Marine Biological Association, is used in the pilot Blue-Cloud Demonstrator [“Zoo and Phytoplankton EOY products”](#). This Blue-Cloud demonstrator aims to obtain phytoplankton, zooplankton, and nutrients EOY products that contribute to improving our knowledge and reduce uncertainty regarding the state of marine plankton ecosystems, as well as their response to ongoing and future climate change.

The collaboration with Blue-Cloud allows to search for EurOBIS biodiversity data in the Blue-Cloud Discovery and Access Service, and to use the data in the Blue-Cloud VRE.

Partners involved: VLIZ

URL: <http://www.eurobis.org/>

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/eurobis-emodnet-biology>

2.2.6. ICOS - Marine

About

ICOS is an international organisation of thirteen European member countries and over 130 greenhouse gas measurement stations aimed at quantifying and understanding the greenhouse gas balance of Europe and neighbouring regions. ICOS data is made available at the Carbon Portal, a one-stop shop for all ICOS data products. The Ocean Thematic Centre is one of four central facilities within the European research infrastructure Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS).

The marine element of ICOS provides long-term oceanic observations, which are required to understand the present state and better predict future behaviour of the global carbon cycle and climate-relevant gas emissions. The Ocean Thematic Centre currently coordinates twenty-one ocean stations from seven countries monitoring carbon uptake and fluxes in the North Atlantic, Nordic Seas, Baltic, and the Mediterranean Sea. Measuring methods include sampling from research vessels, moorings, buoys, and commercial vessels that have been equipped with state-of-the-art carbonate system sensors. The objective is to ensure high quality measurements of greenhouse gas concentrations that are independent, transparent and reliable. In turn, this monitoring system will support governments in their efforts to mitigate climate change as well as holding them accountable for reaching their mitigation targets.

ICOS Structure and Data Flow

Figure 13 Overview of ICOS Data Flow and Organisation

Type & number of data sets

The ICOS Carbon Portal provides observation data from over 130 greenhouse gas measurement stations. Through the SOCAT portal there are around 6000 trajectories available from 1957-2018 with 26 million data values.

Core Services

This concerns two relevant portals: ICOS Carbon Portal with data discovery and access and SOCAT portal with data products. Several services are available for both. Data from official certified ICOS

stations can be accessed at the ICOS Carbon Portal and on an international scale including non ICOS data at the SOCAT Portal. Web services for discovery are existing, but it might be needed to specify and develop API's for data access as part of the Blue-Cloud activities.

- ICOS Carbon Portal (<https://data.icos-cp.eu/portal/> & <https://meta.icos-cp.eu/sparqlclient/>)
- SOCAT Portal (<https://www.socat.info>)

Function in Blue-Cloud

ICOS is one of the nine complementary data infrastructures, that is federated as part of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service. This way, it and serves as the pillars of the initial Blue-Cloud framework. The University of Bergen is contributing, with other partners of the project, to the Blue-Cloud Demonstrator “[Marine Environmental Indicators](#)”. This pilot Demonstrator aims to showcase an online service with an associated cloud-based analytical computing framework and a dedicated web interface to provide and display indicators and information on the environmental quality of the ocean, for the benefit of both researchers and policymakers.

Partners involved: University of Bergen

URL: <https://www.icos-cp.eu/>

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/icos-marin>

2.2.7. SeaDataNet

About

SeaDataNet is a major pan-European infrastructure for managing, indexing and providing access to marine data sets and data products, acquired by European organisations from research cruises and other observational activities in European coastal marine waters, regional seas and the global ocean. Founding partners are National Oceanographic Centres (NODCs), major marine research institutes, UNESCO-IOC, ICES, and EC-JRC.

The SeaDataNet network was initiated in the nineties and over time its network of data centres and infrastructure with standards, tools, and services has expanded, inter alia with support of many EU projects such as Sea-Search, EuroCore, EuMarsin, EuroSeismics, BlackSeaScene, Upgrade-BlackSeaScene, GeoSeas, MicroB3, and in the last 10 years as part of SeaDataNet, SeaDataNet 2, ODIP 1 & 2, EMODnet projects, and SeaDataCloud. There is close cooperation with various other ocean observing communities such as EuroGOOS, as well as with other major marine data management initiatives and infrastructures, in particular with European Marine Observation and Data network (EMODnet) and Copernicus Marine Environmental Monitoring Service (CMEMS).

SeaDataNet develops, governs and promotes common standards, vocabularies, software tools, and services for marine data management, which are freely available from its portal and widely adopted and used. Moreover, the SeaDataNet network of data centres maintains and publishes a series of European directory services which are widely used. These give a wealth of data and information, such as overviews of marine organisations in Europe, and their engagement in marine research projects, managing large datasets, and data acquisition by research vessels and monitoring programmes for the European seas and global oceans.

Type & number of data sets

The CDI service is a SeaDataNet core service and it provides online unified discovery and access to vast resources of data sets, managed by > **110 connected SeaDataNet data centres** from **34 countries** around European seas. Currently it gives access to more than **2.8 Million data sets**, originating from more than 850 organisations in Europe, covering physical, geological, chemical, biological and geophysical data, and acquired in European waters and global oceans.

Core Services

A core SeaDataNet service is the Common Data Index (CDI) data discovery and access service which provides harmonized discovery and access to a large volume of marine and ocean data sets, both from research and monitoring organisations, which increasingly are major input for developing added-value services and products that serve users from government, research and industry.

The online CDI User Interface gives users powerful search options and a highly detailed insight in the availability and geographical spreading of marine data sets, that are managed by the connected data centres. The User Interface includes functions for requesting access, and if granted, for downloading data sets from all connected data centres.

The architecture of the latest version of the CDI service is illustrated in the following image:

Figure 14 CDI system architecture

SeaDataNet operates the CDI data discovery and access service. For exchange to the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service it features an INSPIRE compliant API at aggregate metadata level and a data access API with Marine-ID authentication, capable of processing data requests at the aggregate metadata level.

Main operators are: MARIS, IFREMER, BODC, HCMR, and EUDAT members (CSC, CINECA, GRNET, DKRZ, and STFC). Data Providers: currently >110 data centres consisting of NODCs, marine research institutes, hydrographic surveys, geological institutes, environmental monitoring agencies, international organisations, and some industry.

Figure 15 New dynamic user interface of the upgraded CDI data discovery and access service

Function in Blue-Cloud: SeaDataNet is one of the blue data infrastructures, federated in the Blue-Cloud DD&AS, and serves as one of the pillars of the initial Blue-Cloud framework. Furthermore, use is made of the experiences and system components as developed by SeaDataNet for the upgraded CDI data discovery and access service.

Partners involved: MARIS, Ifremer, CSC, CINECA, DKRZ, VLIZ

URL: <https://cdi.seadatanet.org/search>

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/seadatanet>

2.2.8. SOCAT

About

The Surface Ocean CO₂ Atlas (SOCAT) is a synthesis activity for quality-controlled, surface ocean fCO₂ (fugacity of carbon dioxide) observations by the international marine carbon research community (>100 contributors). SOCAT data is publicly available, discoverable and citable. SOCAT enables quantification of the ocean carbon sink and ocean acidification and evaluation of ocean biogeochemical models. SOCAT, which celebrated its 10th anniversary in 2017, represents a milestone in biogeochemical and climate research and in informing policy.

Type & number of data sets

SOCAT data are released in versions. Each succeeding version contains new data sets as well as updates of older ones. The first version of SOCAT was released in 2011, the second and third version followed biennially. Automation allowed annual public releases since version 4. The latest SOCAT version (version 2021) has **30.6 million** observations from 1957 to 2020 for the global oceans and coastal seas. Calibrated sensor data are also available.

SOCAT version 2021 was released on the 15th of June 2021, containing data submitted on or before 15th of January 2021. Data submissions for the next version are welcome at any time, and will be included in the next SOCAT release in 2022.

Core Services

SOCAT is a core Global Ocean Observing System data product for biogeochemistry endorsed by the Global Ocean Observing System GOOS. This Surface Ocean CO₂ Atlas (SOCAT) data set serves a wide range of user communities. Two distinct data products are available:

- a 2nd level quality controlled global surface ocean fCO₂ data set,
- a gridded SOCAT product of monthly surface water fCO₂ means on a 1° x 1° grid with no temporal or spatial interpolation.

Function in Blue-Cloud

SOCAT is one of the nine blue data infrastructures, federated in the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service.

Partners involved: University of Bergen

URL: <https://www.socat.info/>

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/data-infrastructures/socat>

2.3. Ongoing synergies with projects and initiatives

Blue-Cloud has established synergies in the Open Science, Blue Economy and Marine Research fields with E-infrastructures, Blue Data Infrastructures, and EU-funded projects as the project team believes that through collaboration and cooperation with initiatives operating in the same field, the value of Blue-Cloud services increases.

Below we present a list of all the synergies established, the collaborative activities performed and the outcomes achieved. Per each synergy a digital factsheet is also available online, linked in each of the paragraphs below.

2.3.1. AANChOR – All-Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation

<p>BUILDING AN ALL ATLANTIC OCEAN COMMUNITY Implementing the Belém Statement</p>	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: https://allatlanticocean.org/</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Geonardo Environmental Technologies</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Portugal</p> <p>Project duration: 01/10/2018 - 30/09/2022</p> <p>Funding Programme: H2020-EU.3.2. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine, maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <p>Joint communication & Dissemination</p>	

Project Mission

The All-Atlantic Cooperation for Ocean Research and innovation (AANChOR) is a European Union H2020 whose main ambition is to promote the implementation of the South Atlantic Research and Innovation Flagship initiative and the Belém Statement (BS), signed by the European Union (EU), Brazil, and South Africa in 2017, to upscale research and innovation cooperation in the Atlantic Ocean, from Antarctica to the Arctic, started under the Galway Statement.

AANChOR pursues this ambition by providing the Belém Co-Chairs with a framework to identify and contribute to the implementation of concrete long-term collaborative activities, reinforcing international cooperation between Europe, the tropical and South Atlantic countries, connecting with the challenges and research needs of the North Atlantic. By connecting major players in research and innovation from around the Atlantic Ocean, AANChOR aims to build a long-lasting Atlantic Research and Innovation Ocean Community to address grand challenges and opportunities.

Type of synergy with Blue-Cloud

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and AANChOR have strongly cooperated together in the dissemination and communication area. The cooperation spanned from the

organisation of joint events to promotional activities on social media channels to share the projects' results and reach a broader community.

The projects also co-wrote a joint policy brief "[Nourishing Blue Economy and Sharing Ocean Knowledge - Ocean information for sustainable development](#)" together with the projects EuroSea, AtlantECO, ATLAS, iAtlantic, Nautilus, EUROFLEETS and Odyssea. The policy brief lists recommendations for sustainable ocean observation and management and was developed in the scope of [Horizon Results Booster](#).

The table below presents the events co-organised by Blue-Cloud and AANChOR:

Event title	Date	Event scope
Improving the knowledge of our oceans and seas and bringing them closer to citizens	5 February 2020	Contribute to the implementation of the Galway and the Belém Statements by better understanding the international data/e-infrastructure landscape and the needed federation efforts to accelerate the establishment of a global "Blue-Cloud" able to effectively and efficiently bring data at the service of society
All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum 2020	6 – 7 February 2020	Forum to showcase the results of cooperation and their impact on the citizens living on the shores of the Atlantic
Towards an All Atlantic Data Space	3 June 2021	Co-organisation of a joint workshop as a side event at the All-Atlantic 2021 . The workshop provided an arena to share the current capability of marine data collection, sharing and services across the Atlantic Ocean, and to debate about EU and international initiatives working to harmonise and facilitate data sharing across the Atlantic, and offered insight into available facilities, tools, training, and the latest open science 'blue cloud' technologies to make data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
Blue-Cloud: An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research across the Atlantic and beyond	14 December 2021	Presentation of the joint policy brief developed in the framework of the EC-funded Horizon Results Booster
South African Webinar & Virtual Workshop	24 May 2022	Participation into the scientific forum to support the dialogue towards sustainable perspectives, priorities and activities connected to the All-Atlantic Declaration

Table 3 List of events co-organised and attended by Blue-Cloud and AANChOR

Factsheet available at <https://blue-cloud.org/synergies/aanchor-%E2%80%93-all-atlantic-cooperation-ocean-research-and-innovation>

2.3.2. Aqua-Lit - (Preventive measures for averting the discarding of litter in the marine environment from the aquaculture industry)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.aqua-lit.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Geonardo Environmental Technologies</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Hungary</p> <p>Project duration: 01.09.2019 - 28.02.2021</p> <p>Funding Programme: EASME/EMFF/2017/1.2.1.12 - Sustainable Blue Economy</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; flex-wrap: wrap; gap: 10px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid purple; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid gray; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> <div style="border: 1px solid blue; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> </div>	

Project Mission

The project AQUA-LIT has worked together with the aquaculture stakeholders from the Mediterranean Sea, the Baltic Sea and the North Sea, to develop a toolbox of solutions, measures and recommendations to better handling marine litter from a prevention to a recycling state, further aiming to make the aquaculture industry a leading sector on addressing this global and escalating issue.

Type of synergy with Blue-Cloud

In January 2022 Blue-Cloud and AQUA-LIT signed a **Memorandum of Understanding** highlighting four main action points for collaboration:

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: AQUA-LIT's data on marine litter, coming from aquaculture activities, can be integrated to the Blue-Cloud Aquaculture VRE, or if possible, to a new VRE linked to marine litter data. The connection with Blue-Cloud allows AQUA-LIT's data to be further disseminated and accessible to other stakeholders and researchers also after the termination of the AQUA-LIT project (February 2021).

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: AQUA-LIT data sources can be integrated in the Blue-Cloud dataset through the EMODnet Chemistry infrastructure.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: AQUA-LIT project developed 58 policy recommendations that could be useful to shape the Blue-Cloud roadmap. AQUA-LIT policy is a ready-document that highlights what is needed in terms of policies, governance, support, responsibility, and many other points, to achieve the SDGs goals by 2030.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and AQUA-LIT have supported the promotion of events and workshops to share the projects' results and reach a broader community.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/aqua-lit

2.3.3. AtlantECO - (Atlantic ECOsystems assessment, forecasting & sustainability)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: https://www.atlanteco.eu/</p> <p>Project Coordinator: STAZIONE ZOOLOGICA ANTON DOHRN</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Italy</p> <p>Project duration: 01.09.2020 - 31.08.2025</p> <p>Funding Programme: H2020-EU.3.2. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine, maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy / H2020-BG-2018-2020</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div data-bbox="209 898 619 954" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 25%;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div data-bbox="628 898 1051 954" style="border: 1px solid #90EE90; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 25%; color: #90EE90;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <div data-bbox="209 958 619 1014" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 25%; color: #4682B4;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> </div>	

Project Mission

The EU-funded AtlantECO project aims to develop and apply a novel, unifying framework that provides knowledge-based resources for a better understanding and management of the Atlantic Ocean and its ecosystem services. AtlantECO will engage with citizens and actors from the industry and policy sectors in order to stimulate responsible behaviour and Blue Growth. The project focuses on three pillars of research: microbiomes, plastic and the plastisphere, and seascape connectivity. In pursuit of this goal, AtlantECO is bringing together experts and pioneers from Europe, South America and South Africa with the relevant resources, knowledge and experience.

Type of synergy with Blue-Cloud

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: AtlantECO aims to use the Blue-Cloud DD&AS results to make the connection between imaging, genomics and environmental data, while running the AtlantECO data analysis pipelines and delivering the resulting data products for EMODnet (several EMODnet data infrastructures are involved in Blue-Cloud). Furthermore, AtlantECO is significantly extending the relevant data available to Blue-Cloud and its demonstrators through its systematic and harmonised data management processes for its several cruises and sampling campaigns. Its newly collected data sets are populated into Blue Data Infrastructures such as EurOBIS and ELIXIR - ENA, by which these data become also part of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS offer.

Blue-Cloud benefits from AtlantECO by accessing new data on microbiomes, the plastisphere and carbon fluxes that support ecosystems at basin, as well as from AtlantECO prediction of the cumulative impacts of multiple stressors on ecosystem status and dynamics and ES provision, identifying their drivers and role on tipping points, assessing their changes in recovery of ecosystem structures, functions and services, and developing eco-socio-economic models to predict future

trajectories. These factors have a great impact in the Blue ecosystem and, therefore, have potential to be reflected on the numbers produced by Blue-Cloud Demonstrators.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: The Atlantic marine ecosystems assessed by AtlantECO have brought important inputs for the Blue-Cloud Roadmap, a document which considers the technical developments, market analysis and opportunities for exploitation of Blue-Cloud, while providing options that ensure sustainability of Blue-Cloud services and integration into the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) in the long term. Blue-Cloud roadmap also benefited from the strategy AtlantECO is delivering on capacity building and transfer of knowledge for a seamless engagement between science, industry, policy, and society. It has been a relevant addition for Blue-Cloud Roadmap as this project has partners not only from Europe but also from America and Africa, with inputs from experts from other continents.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and AtlantECO have supported the promotion of events and workshops to share the projects' results and reach a broader community.

In addition, AtlantECO has invited the Blue-Cloud project coordinator, Sara Pittonet to join the AtlantECO podcast series dedicating the episode on 23rd November to Blue-Cloud.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/atlanteco

2.3.4. BeOpen (European forum and oBsErvatory for OPEN science in transport)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>Url: www.beopen-project.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Centre for Research and Technology Hellas / Hellenic Institute of Transport</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Greece</p> <p>Project duration: 01/01/2019 - 30/06/2021</p> <p>Funding Programme - H2020-EU.3.4. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Smart, Green And Integrated Transport</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration+</p> <p>Joint communication & Dissemination</p>	

Project mission

The overarching vision of BE OPEN is to create a common understanding on the practical impact of Open Science and to identify and put in place the mechanisms to make it a reality in transport research. Openness, transparency, fairness, reproducibility of science are key aspects around which BE OPEN seeks to establish the ground rules for the transport research communities, ultimately creating a community of transport research organisations willing to work on the basis of a commonly agreed "Open Science Code of Conduct".

Type of synergy

Joint dissemination/communication activities: The projects have co-organised joint events to share the projects' results and reach a broader community. A practical example is coming from the organisation of the workshop "[Channeling open science for a sustainable management of the ocean](#)" as a side event of the Open Science FAIR 2021, that Blue-Cloud has done together with BE OPEN, Cos4Cloud and FNS-Cloud.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/be-open

2.3.5. CoastObs (Commercial service platform for user-relevant coastal water monitoring services based on Earth observation)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>Url: www.coastobs.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Water Insight B.V.,</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Netherlands</p> <p>Project duration: 01/11/2017 - 30/04/2021</p> <p>Funding Programme - H2020-EU.2.1.6.3. - Enabling exploitation of space data & H2020-EU.2.1.6.1.2. - Boost innovation between space and non-space sectors</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div data-bbox="209 1263 624 1323" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #f0f0f0;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div data-bbox="632 1263 1050 1323" style="border: 1px solid #90EE90; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #e0ffe0;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div>	

Project mission

CoastObs aims to develop innovative EO-based products (monitoring of seagrass and macroalgae, phytoplankton size classes, primary production, and harmful algae) and higher-level products (indicators and integration with predictive models).

CoastObs also aims to establish sustainable supply chains that can be directly integrated into the users' systems. The CoastObs consortium aims to define user groups with common requirements, so tailored products can be developed at highly reduced costs per user. Setup of efficient data structures (array database) for smart (re)processing of data is part of this ambition.

Type of synergy

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: During specific technical meetings, CoastObs offered the willingness to test data linked to its main research (seagrass, macroalgae, phytoplankton, primary production, and harmful algae) in order to make it part of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS offer. In practice, this would have required CoastObs to populate their test data sets in the leading European marine data management infrastructures such as SeaDataNet,

EurOBIS, and others. However, due to lack of time and resources from CoastObs, this action could not be brought forward.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: CoastObs and Blue-Cloud have supported each other in promoting events organised by the respective teams to reach a wider community of experts.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/coastobs

2.3.6. Cos4Cloud (Co-designed citizen observatories for the EOS-Cloud)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.cos4cloud-eosc.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Spain</p> <p>Project duration: 1/11/2019- 28/2/2023</p> <p>Funding Programme H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div style="border: 1px solid #90EE90; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%; color: #90EE90;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 30%; margin-top: 5px;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div>	

Project mission

Cos4Cloud is addressing the challenge of providing data quality to citizens by developing ten technological services to improve citizen science platforms, also known as citizen observatories, to help them boost the quantity and the quality of observations and ensure their long-term viability. Cos4Cloud makes these services available in the new European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), a virtual space aimed at the European scientific community, in order to make them available to anyone interested in creating or improving their citizen observatory.

Moreover, the cutting-edge technologies help improve interoperability, networking, data quality and secure management of data in citizen observatories, with a very user-friendly focus.

Cos4Cloud makes these services available in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Type of synergy

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: Cos4Cloud data can be integrated to the Blue-Cloud infrastructure and in particular its DD&AS, for which the Cos4Cloud data should be populated in the leading European BDIs. During the project, Cos4Cloud has considered following this approach; however, so far this has not resulted in action.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: Cos4Cloud played a relevant role in shaping the strategic Blue-Cloud Roadmap as it provides support in better outlining the Blue-Cloud community, integrating EOSC systems and scaling up Blue-Cloud demonstrators.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Jaume Piera, Cos4Cloud coordinator, is a member of the Blue-Cloud ESEB team. Thanks to his expertise, he has been invited to join the Blue-Cloud workshop on open science and its thematic demonstrators on 23 March 2021.

The Cos4Cloud team Jaume Piera also helped with the co-organisation of the workshop “Channeling open science for a sustainable management of the ocean” as a side event of the Open Science FAIR 2021, together with Blue-Cloud has done together with BE OPEN and FNS-Cloud.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/cos4cloud

2.3.7. DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.doorsblacksea.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: GeoEcoMar</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Romania</p> <p>Project duration: 1/06/2021- 31/5/2025</p> <p>Funding Programme H2020-EU-3.2.3.3 - Boosting marine and maritime innovation through biotechnology</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; flex-wrap: wrap; gap: 10px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 5px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 5px; padding: 5px; width: 30%; background-color: #e0e0ff;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 5px; padding: 5px; width: 30%;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> </div>	

Project mission

DOORS (Developing Optimal and Open Research Support for the Black Sea) is a research project that links citizens, science, and industry for critical Black Sea regeneration, stimulating a new wave of blue economy opportunities. In particular, the project aims to harmonise scientific approaches and policy across all Black Sea nations while bringing access to state-of-the-art satellite technology that allows a better understanding of the entire Black Sea.

Type of synergy

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: DOORS has shared inputs and best practices for the development of the Blue-Cloud strategic Roadmap.

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: Blue-Cloud and DOORS have explored the possibility of creating a dedicated Vlab in the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (“VRE”) in

order to perform dedicated analysis for Black Sea data. A number of meetings took place to discuss the technical requirements and potential benefits. However, due to the impact of the war in Ukraine, activities have been delayed.

Data Discovery and Access Service: Blue-Cloud and DOORS have also discussed how new Black Sea data to be collected by DOORS might become part of the Blue-Cloud DD&AS. Blue-Cloud has strongly recommended to DOORS to manage the new data first of all in the Black Sea NODCs and then to make use of the European BDIs such as SeaDataNet and EurOBIS for sharing the new data at European level. This way, the new data will automatically become part of the Blue-Cloud federation. The DOORS Black Sea partners have agreed with this approach and strategy for new data; however, due to the war situation in the Black Sea region, it was not been possible to undertake project cruises as earlier planned. In the meantime, the dialogue between Blue-Cloud and DOORS is continued and for instance, there were several presentations contributed by SeaDataNet and Blue-Cloud to the MARBLUE Conference, organised in Romania, 26-28 October 2022.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/doors

2.3.8. ENVRI-FAIR (ENVironmental Research Infrastructures building Fair services Accessible for society, Innovation and Research)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.envri-fair.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Forschungszentrum Juelich</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Germany</p> <p>Project duration: 01/01/2019 - 31/12/2022</p> <p>Funding Programme: H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. - Developing new world-class research infrastructures</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div data-bbox="209 1532 624 1588" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div data-bbox="632 1532 1034 1588" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> </div> <div style="margin-top: 10px;"> <div data-bbox="209 1599 632 1648" style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div>	

Project mission

The overarching goal of ENVRI-FAIR is to implement FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable) principles in the ENVRI (European Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures) community and connect it to the European Open Science Cloud. ENVRI-FAIR targets the development and implementation of both technical frameworks and policy solutions that make subdomain boundaries irrelevant for environmental scientists and prepare Earth system science for the new Open Science paradigm and truly interdisciplinary science.

Type of synergy

Connecting Data to key European Data Management service providers via Blue-Cloud: As part of ENVRI-FAIR Blue-Cloud has reviewed the FAIRness of data discovery and access services of multiple RIs, divided over 4 domains (marine, atmosphere, terrestrial, life) and analysed how each of the RIs could improve their FAIRness considering services and formats. These improvements are being made, whereby they work together per domain, but also have horizontal exchanges so that domains and RIS can learn from each other and can adopt and adapt common solutions.

To try out and demonstrate the progress in FAIRness, ENVRI-FAIR has also deployed domain Use Cases, like the Marine Data Demonstrator which has a focus on the Marine RIs in ENVRI-FAIR and selected Essential Ocean Variables (EOV's). Moreover, work has been ongoing on the ENVRI Knowledge Base which documents best practices, solutions, etc in the different domains for improving FAIRness. And finally there is work ongoing on a ENVRI Catalogue which will describe in metadata the various services of the RIs in ENVRI-FAIR.

These 3 components together, Use Cases - Knowledge Base - Catalogue, are the ENVRI-HUB, which has a prototype character and can be seen as a proof-of-concept to demonstrate the outcome of the ENVRI-FAIR activities. It is fully focused on metadata.

Sustainable results of ENVRI-FAIR are the improved and upgraded services at each of the RIs and their increased mutual coherence as well as the methodologies and documentation applied in ENVRI-FAIR for achieving these results.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: ENVRI-FAIR supports the development of the Blue-Cloud roadmap from a strategic point of view, providing insights into the EU Digital Twin Ocean. Moreover, several marine partners and Blue Data Infrastructures from Blue-Cloud participated in the ENVRI-FAIR FAIRness exercise and the marine EOv demonstrator. The resulting insights and improvements have positively contributed to the design and development of the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud has joined the ENVRI Week in Dresden on 3-7 February 2020 in a poster session focussed on highlighting the main goals of the project. [Andreas Petzold](#), ENVRI-FAIR Project coordinator, joined the Round Table *“Building and bringing a thriving marine Open Science community into EOSC: Opportunities & outstanding challenges”* at the [Blue-Cloud Final event](#) in Brussels, on the 8th of December 2022.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/envri-fair

2.3.9. EOSC Future (Improving and Integrating European Ocean Observing and Forecasting Systems for Sustainable use of the Ocean)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.eoscfuture.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: ARC</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Greece</p> <p>Project duration: 01/04/2021 - 30/09/2023</p> <p>Funding Programme - H2020-EU.1.4. - EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <p>Joint communication & Dissemination</p>	

Project mission

The EU-funded EOSC Future project aims to integrate, consolidate and connect e-infrastructures, research communities and initiatives in Open Science to advance the EOSC platform of services (EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange, Interoperability Framework). A major challenge in the project is to make a bridge between the e-infrastructures such as EGI, EUDAT, and GEANT, and the Research Infrastructures, organised in 5 science clusters. The project aims at onboarding of RI services into the EOSC marketplace in order to reach out to a larger audience of potential users, but also at Research Infrastructures adopting EOSC Core services in order to achieve more integration. For this purpose, there is a large workpackage in EOSC-FUTURE dedicated to so-called Cluster Science Projects, which target prototyping multidisciplinary services, led by RIs, and adopting several EOSC core services. These use cases aim to demonstrate that the potential of European research can be supported and accelerated by connecting the major stakeholders in the EOSC ecosystem, developing scientific use cases in collaboration with the thematic communities, engaging the broader EOSC community and increasing its visibility.

Type of synergy

Joint dissemination/communication activities:

During the course of the project Blue-Cloud started a pro-active approach towards the EOSC community to increase awareness about the Blue-Cloud Open platform as a great example of implementation of the three main components of the EOSC Federation - EOSC-Core, EOSC-Exchange

and the Federation of Data & Data Services - into a unique Open Science platform accessible and usable by other research communities.

With the objective to showcase the project's unique approach to Data federation, valuable also for many other thematic communities in the EOSC ecosystem, Blue-Cloud organised a workshop titled *“Blue-Cloud Open Science platform as a model for a sustainable Data federation in EOSC”* at the EOSC Symposium 2022, the main EOSC annual event that took place in Prague, Czech Republic, from 14th-17th November 2022 as part of the calendar of events of the Czech presidency of the Council of the EU. Details and outcomes of the event are collected in a [dedicated page on the Blue-Cloud website](#) and further reported in D5.4

In addition, as part of its dissemination activities, the EOSC Future project developed a series of EOSC in practice stories, to showcase use cases of EOSC tools or services, and share best practices for researchers, data experts and service providers in their daily jobs to inspire further uptake. Dick Schaap, Blue-Cloud technical coordinator and Pasquale Pagano, Blue-Cloud VRE Manager, were interviewed to showcase the technical impact of Blue-Cloud. As an outcome two EOSC in practice stories were prepared, one dedicated to the [Data Discovery and Access Service \(DD&AS\)](#) and one on the Virtual Research Environment that is going to be delivered in April 2023.

EOSC in practice story #11

EOSC Future

Keywords: #EOSC, #Data, #Access, #Discovery, #Infrastructure, #MarineEconomy, #EOSCinPractice #BlueEconomy

Supporting marine data discovery and accessibility to enable cross-domain research

An EOSC in Practice story where a common interface is provided for discovery and retrieval of marine data

The project involved

Blue-Cloud

Blue-Cloud is the flagship initiative of the Horizon Future of the sea and ocean programme of the European Commission (Grant Agreement no 842406). The project delivers a collaborative virtual environment to enhance Data and Open Science in the marine domain. Started in October 2019, Blue-Cloud is displaying a major platform with cross-federation of an unprecedented wealth of multidisciplinary data resources, analytical tools, and computing facilities to explore and demonstrate the potential of cloud-based Ocean Science and address ocean sustainability. EU Green Deal, UN Ocean Decade, and CT Future of the Ocean objectives.

The Challenge

There are several research infrastructures or other data services existing in Europe that create a multitude of multi-related services, providing specific releases coming from observations collected with different methods. These infrastructures constitute a diverse mosaic, each holding a piece of the big picture. Blue-Cloud aims to overcome fragmentation and create a bridge between thematic clusters – such as human-made climate, food and agriculture resources and EOSC – creating data federation and providing common access to so-called thematic EOSC for marine data to enhance the visibility and discoverability of data from marine and environmental domains.

The solution – Data Discovery and Access Service

To overcome the fragmentation, a dedicated Data Discovery and Access Service has been implemented. This service facilitates discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products for several marine data and data products, also interoperable with other Blue-Cloud services, such as the Virtual Research Environment. More than 10 million data sets are managed in Blue-Cloud services (EOSC) that are connected to the Blue-Cloud service to serve federated discovery and access. A common interface is provided for discovery and retrieval of data sets and data products from each of the federated EOSC. The interface also includes facilities for mapping and viewing the location of data sets, as well as part of the query dialogues. Moreover, the interface has a shopping mechanism, enabling users to compare and extend related shopping baskets with requests for data sets from multiple EOSC. This service is provided on a double level. At the first level, users can identify interesting data collections in an aggregated way in a common catalogue in industry entries from the federated EOSC. At the second level, users can get more specific and granular data.

The service provider

MARIS E.V. is a private company located in Hoornbrug (The Netherlands), specialised in developing web-based services and applications in the fields of geographic data management, geographic interfaces and webinars with complex information aims.

The Users

Researchers in the marine environment can exploit Blue-Cloud services to find a broad variety of marine data and resources. More generally, researchers in other areas, such as environmental and social sciences, climate sciences, as well as business and industry players, can discover and use marine data for cross-domain research.

Why do I need EOSC?

- Blue-Cloud services will bring the following benefits to their users being a provider or EOSC:
 - A pilot thematic EOSC as a role model for the development of other thematic clouds. The interoperability of Blue-Cloud provides FAIR access to multidisciplinary data, analytical tools and computing and storage facilities that support research.
 - Blue-Cloud Services showcased through the [Data Discovery and Access Service](#) for ocean, sea and freshwater bodies for ecosystem research, conservation, forecasting and innovation in the Blue Economy, and making innovative use of seamless access to multidisciplinary data, algorithms, and computing resources – accelerating cross-disciplinary science.
 - A methodology for researchers interacting with infrastructure developers to establish a cyber platform with tools and services, which support multiple scientific challenges and are fit-for-purpose, while built upon generic core principles and services.
 - A mechanism to easily access and discover blue data. Blue-Cloud partners manage important volumes of blue data (e.g. SeaWiFS, CHOCat, CHOCat, etc.) and data have been established with major European observatory networks to increase the data volume.
 - APIs to access blue services that will complement EOSC base services providing blue thematic functionalities.
 - Dynamic examples of how a framework like Blue-Cloud can address one or several of the policy challenges defined in the Blue Economy Strategy, the Circular Economy Strategy, the Blue Growth Strategy, the Common Fisheries Policy, the Maritime Spatial Planning Strategy, the Marine Strategy Framework Directive, the International Ocean Governance Communication and the UN SDGs.
 - A global Blue Economy community close to the EOSC vision, including the marine and marine life industry.
 - The opportunity of bringing EOSC in the Blue Economy long-term vision via the policy-oriented [BlueCloud Strategy 2022](#) which sets a series of 20 Calls for further development and update of the Blue Cloud by multiple VRS applications and connecting a global marine data infrastructure.

Societal impact

The [Marine Strategy Framework Directive](#), the [Business Strategy for a more sustainable economy](#), the [Sustainable Development Goals](#) set up by the United Nations and obviously the [EU Green Deal](#) represent major political measures whose implementation is supported also by the enhanced awareness and visibility that initiatives like Blue-Cloud have on the well-informed European and international environments. Blue-Cloud's role is also to inform interested stakeholders that in order to implement these initiatives and understand if a sustainable practice is feasible, scientists need to study its economic and social impacts. Therefore, a multidisciplinary approach to fundability to plan future business practices.

Useful material related to this story

- Blue-Cloud Data Discovery and Access Service
- Blue-Cloud Infrastructure

Want to learn more about the other services being developed by Blue-Cloud? Read here

Liked this #EOSCinPractice story? Follow @EOSCFuture for more!

Share your own #EOSCinPractice story here

Figure 16 EOSC in practice story on Data Discovery and Access Service

Moreover, in a practical manner, exchanges were established between the Blue-Cloud Data Discovery & Access Service respectively Blu-Cloud VRE Products Catalogue service with the EOSC marketplace, facilitating EOSC users to find and get interested in these Blue-Cloud resources, and then to navigate towards the Blue-Cloud for deeper and wider exploration and exploitation of these services.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/eosc-future

2.3.10. EuroSea (Improving and Integrating European Ocean Observing and Forecasting Systems for Sustainable use of the Ocean)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: https://eurosea.eu/</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Geomar</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Germany</p> <p>Project duration: 01/11/2019 - 31/12/2023</p> <p>Funding Programme - H2020-EU.3.2.5.1. - Climate change impact on marine ecosystems and maritime economy</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="border: 1px solid purple; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin: 5px;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid blue; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin: 5px;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin: 5px; width: fit-content; margin-left: 100px;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div>	

Project mission

EuroSea aims to co-design a new approach that could improve European ocean observing and forecasting services and products by building the community needed for a system that delivers services and products on the ocean, ocean climate, marine ecosystems and their vulnerability to human impacts.

Type of synergy

In February 2022 Blue-Cloud and EuroSea signed a Memorandum of Understanding highlighting four main action points for collaboration:

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: EuroSea is primarily looking at data delivery from the observing activities in the ocean observing networks to data integrators.

EuroSea is also developing two demonstrators: the *Coastal Resilience and Operational Services Demonstrator* that is advancing the collection, quality control, interpretation and use of sea level data to deliver a spatially complete picture of sea level changes, and the *Ocean Health Demonstrator* working with users in Aquaculture, Fisheries, Tourism, and Environmental Agencies to co-create products that help identify and foresee Extreme Marine Events. Due to the similarities of topics, the

aim is to integrate the EuroSea data with the Blue-Cloud infrastructure, making use of the leading European BDIs as aggregators, in order to complement data that the projects might miss from their data value chain and, consequently, improve the quality of the dataset.

EuroSea is willing to scope out to what extent the activities by GOOS on mapping the data flow could benefit from cooperation between the EuroSea and Blue-Cloud.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: Toste Tanhua, EuroSea coordinator, is one the members of the Blue-Cloud ESEB team and has been highly involved in shaping the future of the Blue-Cloud Roadmap from a strategic point of view. This included both the participation in events and submission of open consultations.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and EuroSea have been involved in events in which the projects were giving presentations and providing relevant inputs (e.g. Annual EuroSea meeting, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Forum 2020).

Moreover, EuroSea took part in Horizon Results Booster (HRB) in the project group in which Blue-Cloud was also involved. The main outcome of this cooperation has been translated into a policy brief [“Nourishing Blue Economy and Sharing Ocean Knowledge - Ocean information for sustainable development”](#) whose recommendations have been presented at the event [“Blue-Cloud: An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research across the Atlantic and beyond”](#) in December 2021.

In April 2021 Blue-Cloud and EuroSea organised a joint workshop in the framework of the [Blue Research and Innovation Days](#) organised by the Neanias project.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/eurosea

2.3.11. FNS Cloud (Food Nutrition Security Cloud)

FNS - Cloud Food Nutrition Security	Project Information URL: www.fns-cloud.eu Project Coordinator: RTDS ASSOCIATION Coordinator Country: Austria Project duration: 01/10/2019 - 30/09/2023 Funding Programme: H2020-EU.3.2.2.3. - A sustainable and competitive agri-food industry
Purpose of collaboration <div style="display: flex; flex-wrap: wrap; gap: 10px; margin-top: 10px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid purple; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #e6e6ff;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid blue; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #e6e6ff;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #e6ffe6;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div>	

Project mission

FNS-Cloud aims to develop an on-demand, federated network (cloud infrastructure), supporting access and exploitation of FNS resources, integrated with other thematic clouds and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). In addition, FNS-Cloud fosters advanced methods and Services for user communities, making FNS data more FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and adding-value to publicly funded research for citizens.

Type of synergy

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: FNS-Cloud supports the development of the new FAO uFish dataset, a widely used and cited reference table of Food Composition values of aquatic products. The data are taken from selected publications and undergo a thorough review and validation process that must be replicated in this application. The collaboration between Blue-Cloud and FNS-Cloud brings twofold benefits. On one side, the uFish dataset benefits from EU supported API's, like FOODEX2, available in the FNS-Cloud dataset. On the other side, through uFish, FNS-Cloud will be able to find fully referenced records on Food Composition of aquatic products. The uFish dataset is going to enrich the Blue-Cloud Fishery VRE in terms of GRSF description of fish items in the food-value chain and can contribute to a better understanding of the nutritional contribution of fish to food systems. The data connection can be guaranteed through the exploitation of the D4Science Infrastructure.

The technical collaboration, building on an information analysis of the requirements in FAO for Fisheries and Aquaculture Food Composition Tables in the INFOODS framework, resulted in an application, deployed in a D4Science VRE. For the system design, a MySQL Database interacts with a Angular application through JAVA Spring Boot to add, edit, and remove information related to referenced Food Composition Data. The D4Science infrastructure is used to host the application as a Docker Container, and provides certain aspects of user management. For the output, the D4Science Workspace can be used by select users.

FNS-Cloud and Blue-Cloud data overlap where they describe fisheries products as food items. The two domains thus need to share the same definitions of reference data to achieve semantic interoperability. Without sharing reference data describing species, areas, food-processing and

treatments, and even preparations, data cannot be shared with confidence. Blue Cloud developed uFish to implement FAIR data standards for interoperability by developing the capacity to generate FoodID's; standard descriptions of food items using a standardised approach also in use in FNS-Cloud related FoodExplorer. With uFish, Blue-Cloud delivered the core technical data management component across the Food and Fisheries domain. It can be further developed to cover more domains (other foods) and provides important new classifiers for the geographic and temporal origins of Food items, which are poorly defined in existing classification systems. For instance, with uFish, the UUID's of the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries can be included. These UUID's inform on the geographic provenance, management system, and responsible authority of a food item.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: Karl Presser is one the ESEB members, fully involved in supporting the strategic mission of Blue-Cloud and one of the interviewed stakeholders who brought their vision, input and guidance into the Blue-Cloud Roadmap.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: FNS-Cloud and Blue-Cloud have co-organised and joined events to present the synergic work carried out. An example is given by the joint participation at the [EOSC Symposium 2021](#), where the two projects presented development of the new FAO uFish dataset. Another joined event is represented by the organisation of the workshop "[Channeling open science for a sustainable management of the ocean](#)" as a side event of the Open Science FAIR 2021, that Blue-Cloud has done together with BE OPEN, and Cos4Cloud.

Karl Presser, Premotec GmbH and FNS-Cloud, joined the workshop titled "[Blue-Cloud Open Science platform as a model for a sustainable Data federation in EO SC](#)" organised as part of the EO SC Symposium 2022 in Prague, as well as the Round Table "[Building and bringing a thriving marine Open Science community into EO SC: Opportunities & outstanding challenges](#)" at the [Blue-Cloud final event](#) in Brussels in December 2022.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/food-nutrition-security-cloud-fns-cloud

2.3.12. Forcoast (Earth Observation Services for Fishery, Bivalves Mariculture and Oysterground Restoration along European Coasts)

<p>FORCOAST</p>	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.forcoast.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Sticing Deltares</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Netherlands</p> <p>Project Duration: 01/11/2019 - 30/04/2022</p> <p>Funding programme: H2020-EU.2.1.6.1. - Enabling European competitiveness, non-dependence and innovation of the European space sector & H2020-EU.2.1.6.3. - Enabling exploitation of space data</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <p>Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</p>	

Project mission

FORCOAST aims to develop novel Copernicus-based downstream information services to that offer high-resolution water quality and met-ocean indicators in coastal and near-shore areas, to improve operation, planning and management of different marine activities in the sectors of wild fisheries, oyster grounds restoration, and bivalve mariculture. FORCOAST information services are co-designed with stakeholders, thereby ensuring that these services are tailored to meet their needs.

Type of synergy

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: Forcoast supported the future of the Blue-Cloud project, through advice on how to build the roadmap from industrial and commercial viewpoints through open consultation.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/forcoast

2.3.13. ILIAD (Digital Twin of the Ocean)

	<p>Project Information</p> <p>URL: www.ocean-twin.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: NETCOMPANY - INTRASOFT</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Belgium</p> <p>Project Duration: 01/02/2022 - 31/05/2025</p> <p>Funding programme: H2020-EU.3.2. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine, maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; flex-wrap: wrap; gap: 10px;"> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 45%;">Data Discovery and Access Services</div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 45%;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> <div style="border: 1px solid #ccc; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; width: 45%;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div>	

Project mission

The EU-funded ILIAD project creates an interoperable, data-intensive, and cost-effective Digital Twin of the Ocean (DTO) contributing to the implementation of the European Green Deal. It capitalises on the increasing wealth of data and advanced computing infrastructures by combining these diverse data in a semantically rich and data-agnostic approach allowing simultaneous communication with real-world systems and models. ILIAD also aims to create a marketplace to distribute apps, plug-ins, interfaces, raw data, citizen science data, synthesised information and value-added services.

Type of synergy

Data Access and Discovery Service: the DTO will be a free and unrestricted infrastructure that provides access to all ocean data, software and computational resources to enable increased knowledge and innovation in order to build the digital twin of the ocean. In order to build it, the ILIAD project needs to gather a consistent amount of data related to the ocean and marine environments. Within this infrastructure, Blue-Cloud is seen as one of the founding research components, offering e-infrastructure services (computing, storage, analytical, SSO, AAI and generic services to be orchestrated with a large variety of data resources), federated data and research intensive virtual labs. Hence, the Blue-Cloud infrastructure is a key component to increase quality and quantity of data used to build the DTO.

A first meeting with the ILIAD consortium was organised on 24th June 2022 as an online session, to showcase to each other the projects, their activities and their targeted Key Exploitable Results. This way a first insight was established at both sides and possible ways for collaboration were explored. The slides of the session can be downloaded here <https://data.d4science.net/M3iQ> . ILIAD has a focus on end-user applications and it more or less relies on other developments and infrastructures such as Copernicus Marine and EMODnet for getting access to the required data, data products, and services. From the meeting it appeared, that ILIAD could also make good use from Blue-Cloud services such as the DD&AS for finding and retrieving data sets, and VLabs for analyses. Therefore, it was agreed to keep contact and to explore the options for synergy and actual cooperation further. This will take place in the Blue-Cloud 2026 framework.

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: The cooperation between Blue-Cloud and ILIAD is strategic also in terms of future developments of Blue-Cloud. Plans and developments coming from ILIAD have contributed to building the strategic Blue-Cloud Roadmap in relation with the development of the European Digital Twin.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: Blue-Cloud and ILIAD have joined events where both projects were invited to provide strategic overviews in terms of the future of the DTO. An example is given by “*Digital Ocean Forum*”, organised in April 2022 in Paris by Mercator Ocean, one of the major players in developing the European DTO and Blue-Cloud partner. The outcomes of the event are collected in a [dedicated article](#).

ILIAD was also invited to join the [Blue-Cloud final event](#). [Akrivi Vivian Kiouji](#), Netcompany INTRASOFT and member of ILIAD coordination office joined the Round Table “*Delivering a digital marine knowledge system to support the EU Green Deal & UN Agenda 2030: How can Blue-Cloud further contribute to accelerate progress in the marine domain?*”

Sara Pittonet Gaiarin, Coordinator of Blue-Cloud, has also recently been invited to join the ILIAD **Advisory Group**. A meeting is expected to take place over the next few months.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/iliad

2.3.14. JERICO-RI

	<p>Project information</p> <p>URL: https://www.jerico-ri.eu/</p> <p>Project Coordinator: iFREMER</p> <p>Coordinator Country: France</p> <p>Project Duration: 01/02/2020 - 31/01/2024</p> <p>Funding programme: EXCELLENT SCIENCE - Research Infrastructures</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="border: 1px solid purple; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin: 5px;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid blue; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin: 5px;">Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap</div> </div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; margin: 5px; width: fit-content;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div>	

Project Mission

JERICO-RI is an integrated pan-European multidisciplinary and multi-platform research infrastructure dedicated to a holistic appraisal of coastal marine system changes. It aims to bridge existing continental, atmospheric and open ocean RIs, thus filling a key gap in the ESFRI landscape. JERICO-RI establishes the framework upon which coastal marine systems are observed, analysed, understood and forecasted.

JERICO-RI enables open-access to state-of-the-art and innovative facilities, resources, FAIR data and fit-for-purpose services, fostering international science collaboration.

Type of synergy

In April 2022 Blue-Cloud and JERICO signed a Memorandum of Understanding highlighting four main action points for collaboration:

Contribution to Blue-Cloud Roadmap: JERICO shared experiences and skills for the development of the Blue-Cloud strategic Roadmap. In particular, Laurence Delauney was one of the interviewed stakeholders who brought their vision, input and guidance into the Blue-Cloud Roadmap.

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: Blue-Cloud opened an account for JERICO to build a VLab at the Blue-Cloud VRE and gave the necessary guidance and support for this development and deployment. This pilot will be expanded as part of the Blue-Cloud 2026 project in which JERICO is now represented by several of its members for developing a more elaborated VLab.

Joint dissemination/communication activities: [Laurent Delauney](#), Ocean Best Practices System and JERICO-RI joined the Round Table “Building and bringing a thriving marine Open Science community into EOSC: Opportunities & outstanding challenges” at the [Blue-Cloud final event](#) in Brussels in December 2022.

2.3.15. Jonas (Joint Framework for Ocean Noise in the Atlantic Seas)

	<p>Project information</p> <p>URL: www.jonasproject.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: MaREI</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Ireland</p> <p>Project Duration: 01/01/2019 - 30/06/2022</p> <p>Funding programme: 2014 - 2020 INTERREG VB Atlantic Area</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="border: 1px solid purple; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #e6e6ff;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; background-color: #e6ffe6;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div>	

Project mission

JONAS project addresses the issue of underwater noise and the threats it poses to sensitive species in the northeast Atlantic by streamlining ocean noise monitoring and risk management on a transnational basis.

JONAS aims to harmonise technical approaches to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) requirements, promote quieter operational practices among users of the North Europe Atlantic marine space, support adoption of regional-scale approaches that benefit biodiversity and the MSFD implementation, and develop an innovative noise-monitoring visualisation platform supporting adaptive management of sensitive marine areas.

Type of synergy

In October 2021 Blue-Cloud and Jonas signed a **Memorandum of Understanding** highlighting four main action points for collaboration:

Usage and exploitation of Blue-Cloud VRE services: JONAS has expressed interest in developing a dedicated VLab on the Blue-Cloud D4Science infrastructure. The VLab, which has been named after the project, allows JONAS partners to access data collected by Blue-Cloud, while enriching the basin of data and collecting and improving the quality of the analysis. JONAS was one of the projects that attended the online tutorial organised on 7 October 2022 to better explain the VRE offer. It has been designed as a development and integration environment for R, Python, and other supported software languages. Computing resources are assigned dynamically according to the exploitation of the VLab. The VLab has been equipped with the Data Discovery and Access Service and with the Analytics framework (JupyterHub, RStudio, DataMiner, SAI). It is powered by a cluster of Analytics Engine servers, each with 16 cores and 32 GB RAM, a cluster of RStudio servers, each with 16 cores and 32 GB RAM and it is powered by JupyterHub with a maximum of 8 cores and 32 GB RAM per notebook.

The JONAS Virtual Lab is for supporting the Joint Framework for Ocean Noise in the Atlantic Seas initiative. (Access is restricted to project users only).

[Enter the VLab](#)

Figure: Cover of the JOANS Vlab entry page on D4Science

Joint dissemination/communication activities: JONAS and Blue-Cloud have supported each other by promoting events on social media channels and plan to organise joint events to talk about the cooperation established.

Factsheet soon available at www.blue-cloud.org/jonas

2.3.16. NEANIAS (Novel EOSC services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater and Space Challenges)

	<p>Project information</p> <p>URL: www.neanias.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: ETHNIKO KAI KAPODISTRIAKO PANEPISTIMIO ATHINON</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Greece</p> <p>Project Duration: 01/11/2019 - 31/10/2022</p> <p>Funding programme: H2020-EU.1.4.1.3. - Development, deployment and operation of ICT-based e-infrastructures</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <p style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; display: inline-block;">Joint communication & Dissemination</p>	

Project mission

NEANIAS promotes Open Science practices and plays an active role in the materialisation of the EOSC ecosystem by efficiently engaging large scientific and professional communities. It also actively contributes to the technological, procedural, strategic and business development of the EOSC. NEANIAS drives the co-design and delivery of innovative thematic services, derived from state-of-the-art research assets and practices in three major sectors: Underwater research, Atmospheric research and Space research, each engaging multitudinous academic and business groups, numerous researchers, professionals and governmental entities.

Type of synergy

Joint dissemination/communication activities: The collaboration between Blue-Cloud and Neanias focused around joint dissemination activities focused on Underwater and Atmospheric research (Neanias) and Fisheries, Aquaculture and Environmental Marine Indicators demonstrators (Blue-Cloud).

The main action was the organisation of the [“Blue Research and Innovation Days” event](#) organised in April 2021 with the involvement of projects and initiatives in the marine research field to present their objectives, the current results, the possible business cases and to investigate common approaches to specific problems, complementarities, synergies perspectives, future collaborations.

Factsheet soon available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/neanias

2.3.17. ODYSSEA (OPERATING A NETWORK OF INTEGRATED OBSERVATORY SYSTEMS IN THE MEDITERRANEAN SEA)

	<p>Project information</p> <p>URL: http://odysseaplatform.eu</p> <p>Project Coordinator: Professor Georgios SYLAIOS</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Greece</p> <p>Project duration: 01/06/2017 - 30/11/2021</p> <p>Funding Programme - H2020-EU.3.2.5. - Cross-cutting marine and maritime research</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <p>Joint communication & Dissemination</p>	

Project mission

The ODYSSEA project has developed an interoperable and cost-effective platform that fully integrates networks of observing and forecasting systems across the Mediterranean basin, addressing both the open sea and the coastal zone. The platform collects the data from the many databases maintained by agencies, public authorities, and institutions of Mediterranean EU and non-EU countries, integrating existing earth observation facilities and networks in the Mediterranean Sea building on key initiatives such as Copernicus, GEOSS, GOOS, EMODNet, ESFRI, Lifewatch, Med-OBIS, GBIF, AquaMaps, Marine IBA e-atlas, MAPAMED and others with marine and maritime links.

Type of synergy

Joint dissemination/communication activities: ODYSSEA has joined the Horizon Results Booster group where the Blue-Cloud was a member in order to exploit joint dissemination activities. The main outcome of this cooperation has been translated into a policy brief “[Nourishing Blue Economy and Sharing Ocean Knowledge - Ocean information for sustainable development](#)” whose recommendations have been presented at the event “[Blue-Cloud: An Open Science platform for collaborative marine research across the Atlantic and beyond](#)” in December 2021.

Factsheet available at www.blue-cloud.org/synergies/odyssea

3. Towards Blue-Cloud 2026: paving the way for new synergies

Blue-Cloud will continue getting in contact with relevant initiatives in open science, marine research and blue economy to implement technical and outreach collaboration. The synergy programme will be brought forward by the follow-up initiative Blue-Cloud2026. Below we list some of the synergies that were started in the framework of the Blue-Cloud project and that will be continued from March 2023 on.

3.1. EDITO & EDITO Infra

In this context of the [European Green Deal](#) and of the Mission Restore our Ocean and Waters, under Horizon Europe, the development of an [EU Digital Twin of the Ocean](#) is a key priority for Europe. It will be built on existing EU assets, i.e. the complementary services provided by the Copernicus Marine Service and the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet), to improve ocean knowledge and support science-based actionable decision-making based on the next generation of EU digital ocean models and marine information systems and enabling implementation of what-if scenarios.

In addition to the ILIAD DTO project, the EU commission, wanting to scale up the DTO initiative and make it compatible with the Destination Earth program, has started two projects for a EU Public Infrastructure for the European Digital Twin, called EDITO-infra and EDITO Modellab, led by Mercator Ocean International.

EDITO-Infra will be upgrading, combining and integrating key service components of the existing EU ocean observing, monitoring and data programmes Copernicus Marine Service (Copernicus Marine Service) and the European Marine Observation and Data Network (EMODnet) into a single digital framework. As such, [EDITO-Infra](#) will provide the foundation for the further development of the EU DTO initiative, hosting the deployment of multiple DTO applications from ongoing and future digital twin projects, supporting the deployment of new generation of ocean models (e.g. via Horizon Europe underlying models for the European DTO projects) and of the Mission lighthouses projects. on top of this, [EDITO Model Lab](#) will prepare the next generation of ocean models, complementary to Copernicus Marine Service to be integrated into the EU public infrastructure of the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) that will ensure access to required input and validation data (from EMODnet, EuroGOOS, ECMWF, Copernicus Services and Sentinels satellite observations) and to high-performance and distributed computing facilities (from EuroHPC for HPC and other cloud computing resources) and that will be consolidated under developments of Destination Earth (DestinE).

The Blue Cloud project is always referenced as one of the important assets to be integrated in this construction.

The integration of Blue-Cloud assets could be dual. First at data access level, the different datasets available in Blue-Cloud could become part of the Datalake of the EU DTO. This would give continuity to the work of data gathering and organizing made in Blue cloud, while offering users of this data access a solution. Second, the different demonstration projects and the VREs, created in Blue-Cloud,

could be hosted on the service infrastructure of the DTO. This would open some sustainability to the Blue-Cloud project results and enable the community of users and collaborators to get into and maintain these services in a durable way as offered by the EDITO infra platform.

Marina Tonani, Mercator Ocean International, introduced the role of Blue-Cloud with respect to the EDITO projects during the Blue-Cloud final event, in the Round Table “Delivering a digital marine knowledge system to support the EU Green Deal & UN Agenda 2030: How can Blue-Cloud further contribute to accelerate progress in the marine domain?²”.

Figure 17 Roundtable “Delivering a digital marine knowledge system to support the EU Green Deal & UN Agenda 2030” at the Blue-Cloud final event, Brussels, 8 December 2022

² Recordings of the event available at <https://blue-cloud.org/events/blue-cloud-final-conference-open-science-eu-green-deal>

3.2. Aqualnfra

	<p>Project information</p> <p>URL: https://aquainfra.eu/</p> <p>Project Coordinator: AALBORG UNIVERSITET</p> <p>Coordinator Country: Denmark</p> <p>Project duration: 01/01/2023 - 30/12/2026</p> <p>Funding Programme - HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-03 - FAIR and open data sharing in support of healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters</p>
<p>Purpose of collaboration</p> <div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="border: 1px solid purple; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; color: purple;">Cyber infrastructure & VRE</div> <div style="border: 1px solid green; border-radius: 10px; padding: 5px; color: green;">Joint communication & Dissemination</div> </div>	

AquaINFRA is a ‘sister project of Blue-Cloud 2026 as they are both funded through the same Call budget. For that reason, the EU officers encourage a close cooperation in the coming years. Therefore, a first meeting was organised on 15th March 2023, between some core partners of both projects. Presentations were given about the background, overall objectives, and workplans of both projects, followed by a brainstorming. At the meeting, the AquaINFRA technical coordinator indicated that their proposal and workplan was largely inspired and aligned with the Blue-Cloud, hoping that both projects, if funded, would be able to cooperate quite intensively, combining each others strengths to serve the aquatic communities (ocean, marine, coastal, deltas, estuaries, and rivers) in an integrated way. Three potential lines of major cooperation were identified: **a)** expanding the Data Discovery & Access Service with not only more Blue Data Infrastructures, but also with several Freshwater Data Infrastructures; **b)** expanding the Blue-Cloud integrated and smart e-infrastructure ecosystem of D4Science, EUDAT, EGI, and WEkEO, with e-infrastructures as operating in AquaINFRA, and **c)** exchange of experiences at the level of VLab use cases. It was agreed to work out a document formulating the possible cooperation around these 3 lines and a practical methodology for its implementation, that will be evaluated by the project steering committees for mutual acceptance and following deployment.

3.3. MARCO-BOLO & Coastal observations related projects

Project information

URL: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101082021>

Project Coordinator: EMBRC

Coordinator Country: France

Project duration: 01/12/2022 - 30/11/2026

Funding Programme - [HORIZON-CL6-2022-BIODIV-01-01 - Observing and mapping biodiversity and ecosystems, with particular focus on coastal and marine ecosystems](#)

Purpose of collaboration

Blue-Cloud demonstrators & Vlabs

Joint communication & Dissemination

On Tuesday 14th March Blue-Cloud project coordinator Sara Pittonet attended a meeting organised by the MARCO-BOLO project, chaired by Nicolas Pade (EMBRC) to discuss collaboration opportunities with other projects working on Coastal observations. The following projects were present: OBAMA-NEXT, GES4SEAS, BioOcean5D, Biodiversa+, DTO Bioflow, Aqualnra, MBON/University of South Florida, EuropaBON, , EU4OceanOBS, plus ESA.

The meeting discussed the opportunity of organising different "task forces" across these projects to align on activities, maximise effort and re-use technologies, resources and best practices as much as possible. Task forces to be possibly created will cover Essential Variables (**EBV - EOVS**) , **Ocean Observations practices**, technology for mapping biodiversity, coastal observation **modelling**, **stakeholder engagement** and **communications**.

A collaboration within the framework of the Blue-Cloud **Training Academy** was also suggested ,and the projects were invited to propose additional modules dedicated to coastal observation best practices.

4. Conclusions

The second release of the Blue-Cloud Fact Sheets for cluster projects provided an update of the activities performed by the Blue-Cloud project team to establish strong and durable synergies with both research infrastructures and EU-funded projects.

The work presented in this deliverable showcases how relevant it is to create connections with similar projects operating in the same research field due to the opportunity to share joint results to a wider community, making the project results more extensive and not stand-alone.

The Blue-Cloud has achieved to create collaboration with players both at the European and international sphere.

In the next 42 months, Blue-Cloud will continue its journey through the newly-funded project Blue-Cloud 2026. Its aim is to continue strengthening the relationship with the identified initiatives in the first three years of its lifetime and explore new opportunities also in relation with the EOSC and DTO environments.